

Harmonised European Solutions for Testing Automation Road Transport

HEADSTART D.1.2. Stakeholders and user group needs

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List of abbreviations and acronyms

Abbreviation	Meaning
AD	Automated Driving
ADAS	Advanced Driver Assistance Systems
CAD	Connected and Automated Driving (function)
CARTRE	Coordination of Automated Road Transport Deployment for Europe
CATARC	China Automotive Technology and Research Center
DSSAD	Data Storage System for Automated Driving
EDR	Event Data Recorder
ERTRAC	European Road Transport Research Advisory Council
ESV	Enhanced Safety of Vehicles
ETPC	European Truck Platooning Challenge
EV	Electric Vehicles
FOTs	Field Operational Tests
F2F	Face to Face
GRVA	Working Party on Automated/Autonomous and Connected Vehicles
HEADSTART	Harmonised European Solutions for Testing Automated Road Transport
HIL	Hardware In the Loop
HMI	Human Machine Interface
HWC	Highway Chauffeur
JAMA	Japan Automobile Manufacturers Association
KETs	Key Enabling Technologies
MRM	Minimum Risk Manoeuvre
NCAP	New Car Assessment Program
NHTSA	National Highway Traffic Safety Administration
OBD	On-Board Diagnostics
OD	Operational Domain
ODD	Operational Design Domain
OEDR	Object Event Detection and Response
OEM	Original Equipment Manufacturer
OICA	International Organization of Motor Vehicle Manufacturers
PFA	Plateforme de la Filière Automobile (French Automotive Manufacturers Association)
POC	Proof Of Concept
PRT	Personal Rapid Transit
PTI	Periodic Technical Inspection
SAE	Society of Automotive Engineers
SIL	Software In the Loop
SotA	State of the Art
SOTIF	Safety Of The Intended Functionality
TIV	Inter-Vehicular Time
TOR	Take-Over Requests
TT	Test Track
TTC	Time To Collision
VDLF	Vehicle Driving License Framework
V2X	Vehicle to Everything
WG	Working Group

Executive Summary

This deliverable “Stakeholders and user group needs” is presenting the results of the work carried out during the task 1.2. In order to identify and collect the needs of stakeholders and user groups, a series of interviews and surveys carried out on the following topics: Use cases and Scenarios, Safety Assessment, Testing, Certification/ Type approval (tools, procedures), Consumer testing and Testing goal for KETs.

Relevant stakeholders such as Vehicle manufacturers, automotive suppliers, policy makers & member states, consumer organisations and research institutes across the value chain were identified and contacted by the contributors of this task either for being interviewed or to answer an online survey. The identification of needs have benefited from a consultation of relevant stakeholders through the organisation of a workshop gathering task contributors and external experts in close collaboration with T5.1 to share first findings, to collect experts’ views and to propose a prioritisation of use cases.

The needs on use cases and scenarios (chapter 3) are detailing various aspects of the use cases such as their benefits and associated risks, their social acceptability that were used to build a list of prioritised use cases. The functional description of these use cases was also introduced with the minimum system requirements, the system limitation, the Minimum Risk Manoeuvre and the Human-Machine Interface. These needs will serve as a base for the task 1.4 “Functional requirements and use case selection”. Then, the needs for testing, validation and certification for these use cases were discussed with questions on the road infrastructure, traffic, procedures, tools and methodologies. These needs will be useful for the WP3 “procedures, environments and tools”.

The needs identified on the safety of the connected and automated vehicle are detailed in the chapter 4 of this deliverable. The stakeholders gave their opinion on the new risks following the introduction of connected and automated vehicles on the roads. They also showed that the scenario-based approach is the most suitable and will require to collect data in order to build a common scenario database. The legislations and standards for CAD safety were discussed and it is clear that the legal framework needs has to accompany the technological changes brought by the introduction of CAD on the market.

Testing is a key topic in the HEADSTART project. The needs for testing (chapter 5) will be used alongside the state of the art to create a harmonized and generally accepted methodology. Collecting the needs will ensure that the project is aligned with the current activities of stakeholders in the field of testing.

The needs on certification and type approval were identified from relevant technical services and type approval authorities, international organisations and research organisations (chapter 6). The stakeholders expressed a wide point of view on the current gaps and the foreseen steps of the automated vehicle certification. The trends in regulation and in type approval were also detailed. Consumer testing represents a relevant final user of this methodology (chapter 7). The stakeholders were asked about the differences between safety assurance and safety benefits. The role of consumer testing is crucial to ensure CAD safety. For this, the stakeholders expressed their expectations on various topics such as: the rating system for higher level of autonomy, the consumer testing methodology, which scenarios to choose, or the expected test duration for assessing an automated function.

The final topic of interest in this identification of stakeholder needs is the “Testing goal for KETs”(chapter 8). The stakeholders were asked about the best application for testing the three Key Enabling Technologies focussed by HEADSTART : cyber-security, positioning and Communication (V2X). The use cases that have testing goals for KET’s can at the top level be seen to adhere to one of three categories defined by ERTRAC¹ : Automated passenger cars, automated freight vehicles and urban mobility vehicles. The list of situations identified by in this chapter will be exploited in the task 1.3 “Requirement Identification for KETs”.

¹ <https://www.ertrac.org/uploads/documentsearch/id57/ERTRAC-CAD-Roadmap-2019.pdf>

1 Introduction

1.1 Aim of the project

The Connected and Automated Mobility is expected to be an essential component in the pursuit of a safer, cleaner, more efficient and more user-friendly mobility system. For this, EU Member States, industry as well as the European Commission collaborate to achieve the ambitious vision of European Union, taking into consideration public authorities, citizens, cities and industry interests. The introduction and deployment of Connected and Automated Mobility is supported by the European Commission on various levels, such as policy initiatives, policy strategies in collaboration with industries, standards' development, research and innovation projects, etc.

In this context, the main motivation of HEADSTART is the assurance of safety in Connected and Automated Driving. More specifically, HEADSTART, aims to define testing and validation procedures of Connected and Automated Driving (CAD) functions including key technologies such as communications, cyber-security and positioning. HEADSTART will launch the tests in both simulation and real-world fields to validate safety and security performance according to the key users' needs. Its ultimate aim is to bring together the consortium with other European and national CAD stakeholders to cluster the most relevant existing initiatives, develop methodologies, procedures and tools and drive in a harmonized European solution for testing and validation of automated road vehicles.

HEADSTART will identify and harmonise the existing methodologies, procedures and tools and also define and develop test, validation and certification methodologies for CAD functions. In addition, will demonstrate the developed methodologies, procedures and tools through testing up to 4 CAD use cases and reach consensus by creating and managing an expert network to promote adoption of the project results.

1.2 Purpose and scope

The objective of HEADSTART task 1.2 is to gather all relevant stakeholders from various industry clusters and identify their needs on methodologies and procedures, tools and standards from the viewpoint of different user groups.

Five types of user groups were identified:

- Vehicle manufacturers
- Automotive suppliers
- Policy Makers, Member States
- Consumer organisation
- Research institutes

In order to reach our objective, a set of questionnaires were produced on six relevant topics for HEADSTART:

- Use cases and Scenarios
- Safety Assessment and Safety-Case
- Testing
- Certification/ Type approval (tools, procedures)
- Consumer testing
- Testing goal for KETs

Relevant stakeholders across the value chain were identified and contacted by the contributors of this task either for being interviewed or to answer an online survey.

The needs of the stakeholders identified through the interviews were presented to relevant stakeholders, including external experts from organisations that are not directly represented in the consortium. This has been

done through a workshop² on the 12th of June at the Enhanced Safety of Vehicles (ESV) conference to share our first findings and collect the participating experts' views on the prioritisation of use cases.

1.3 Structure of the deliverable

This deliverable is structured into 11 chapters. After the introduction and overview over the deliverable, the chapter two introduces the methodology and approach used for the identification of needs as well as the validation by the expert group. The chapters three to eight are presenting the result for each interview topic. Chapter nine details the outcome of the workshop and the comments of the expert group on the prioritisation of use cases. Chapter ten is an analysis of the user group needs for each topic, collected with the interviews and online surveys. Finally, a conclusion is drawn in chapter 11.

² Description of the workshop in chapter 2.5

2 Methodology

The main objective of the task 1.2 was to identify the needs on methodologies, procedures (demonstrations, certifications) , tools and standards from the viewpoint of different stakeholders and user groups. This feedback is important for the HEADSTART project to guide the work of the following tasks according to the needs identified and ensure that the project is aligned with the current activities of stakeholders involved with CAD.

The identification of user group needs will be done through the following process:

- 1) Identification of the interview topics that fit the scope of the project.
- 2) Allocation of topic leaders: in charge of leading the approach to stakeholder.
- 3) Creation of the interview questionnaires by each topic leader.
- 4) Peer review of the questionnaires.
- 5) Classification and targeting of stakeholders: for each interview topic, within the consortium and with other pertinent organisation identified outside the consortium.
- 6) Interviews with stakeholders.
- 7) Adjusting the questionnaires for the online surveys
- 8) Publish and share the online surveys
- 9) Workshop organisation: Sharing findings with experts & use case prioritisation

2.1 Approach for interviewing the stakeholders

To collect the user group needs, six interview topics were selected, and topic leaders were chosen among the contributors. This selection was based both in the organisation’s expertise as well as their responsibilities in other HEADSTART tasks.

TABLE 1: TOPICS OF INTERVIEW AND TOPIC LEADERS

Topic leaders				
Methodologies, procedures, tools and standards on:	IDIADA	IKA	SAFER	VEDECOM
• Use cases and Scenarios				Leader
• Safety Assessment and Safety-Case				Leader
• Testing		Leader		
• Certification/ Type approval (tools, procedures)	Leader			
• Consumer testing	Leader			
• Testing goal for KETs			Leader	

2.2 Stakeholder identification

Relevant stakeholders were divided into user groups. This allowed to organise the :

TABLE 2: INTERVIEWS AND SURVEYS PER TYPE OF STAKEHOLDER

Type of stakeholder	Number of interviews made	Targeted survey	Total
OEMs	5	3	8
Automotive suppliers / Tier 1	1	2	3
Public authority / Policy makers	3	1	4
Consumer organisation/ Association	0	1	1
Research institutes/ Research projects / Engineering companies/ Proving grounds	11	16	27
Universities	0	1	1
Total	20	24	44

2.3 Conducting the interviews

The first part of the collection of user groups needs on the different topics was made through conducting face to face (F2F) or telephone interviews with experts from the HEADSTART consortium in an effort to collect detailed qualitative answers on our interview topics. In a second phase, relevant external stakeholders were identified by the topic leaders and contacted to be interviewed. The interviews were lasting between 30 minutes and one hour each depending on the topic. Each topic leader has decided on a way to collect the needs of stakeholders:

- For the topics of **“Use cases and Scenarios”** and **“Safety Assessment and Safety-Case”** the needs were collected mostly by face to face or telephone interviews. Some stakeholders that were not available for interviews answered the questionnaire by Email.
- The topic of **“Consumer testing”** and **“Testing”** were made entirely with F2F interviews.
- The topic of **“Certification/ Type approval (tools, procedures)”** used a majority of surveys for their answers.
- The needs on **“Testing goal for KETs”** were collected with an online survey.

The questionnaires and online surveys for each interview topic are available in the annexes of this deliverable.

2.4 Collecting experts needs with a survey

The second part of the collection of user groups needs was made through an online survey in order to reach a broader audience. This online survey was made based on the original interview questionnaires but simplified and with context given to the questions. The aim was to reduce the answering time to the survey to 15 minutes maximum.

These surveys templates were then uploaded to Microsoft forms and published on the HEADSTART website³.

The online survey results were not taken into account for the analysis of the results of this deliverable as they will stay online for a while longer to allow more stakeholders to give their opinion. This will also allow the next tasks

³ <https://www.headstart-project.eu/2019/06/03/your-opinion-matters/>

and work packages to align their work according to the needs of a representative sample of user groups. The deliverable will also be updated into a second release that will include the results of the online survey.

2.5 Workshop organisation: Sharing findings with experts & use case prioritisation

A workshop was organised on June 12th, 2019 at ESV (Enhanced Safety for Vehicles Conference) in Eindhoven (NL) to introduce the objectives of the HEADSTART project to a group of experts from the industry, public authorities and consumer organisations. The goal of this workshop was to collect their opinion on the topics of Use case and scenario selection as well as Consumer testing. A prioritisation of use cases was presented based on the interviews' first results, the views of participating experts on this prioritisation were then collected during an open discussion session. The results of the workshop are detailed in the chapter 9 of this deliverable.

3 Use cases and Scenarios

This chapter introduces the survey and interviews of experts for the topic of use cases and scenarios. Each sub-chapter represents a topic of discussion addressed in the questionnaire. The answers are organised between each type of stakeholder that were interviewed (presented in the figure 1). Use cases and scenarios are important topics for HEADSTART and the priority use cases arising from these interviews will serve as a base for the selection of use cases that will take place in task 1.4.

For the purpose of the interviews, the aim of the questionnaire is to identify the requirements of different types of industry stakeholders on the priority use cases for the industry, their associated scenarios and system requirements. The questionnaire used for this topic of interview is available in the annex 2 of this report.

The definition of a use case for HEADSTART follows the SOTIF⁴ definition: A use case can be defined as “Specification of a generalized field of application, possibly entailing the following information about the system: one or several scenarios; the functional range; the desired behaviour; and the system boundaries”. It is important to note that the use case description typically does not include a detailed list of all relevant scenarios for this use case. Instead a more abstract description of these scenarios is used.

The key stakeholders needs expressed in these interviews will be synthesized in the chapter 10.1 of this report.

The following figure shows the type of stakeholders interviewed for this topic.

FIGURE 1 TYPE OF STAKEHOLDERS – USE CASES AND SCENARIOS

It is important to highlight that some of the research institutes interviewed are also involved in consumer testing, type approval testing and proving ground activities.

⁴ From ISO/PAS 21448:2019 “Road vehicles- Safety of the intended functionality”
<https://www.iso.org/standard/70939.html>

3.1 Priority use cases for CAD testing and validation

This section presents the answers to the question 1, 2 and 15 of the questionnaire:

- 1) What are your use cases for testing and validating a Connected and Automated Vehicle?
- 2) Do you think the use cases that you are currently working on are priority compared to other use cases (e.g. Highway pilot, Valet parking, urban driving, truck platooning ...)? Why?
- 15) In your opinion, what are the priority use cases for certification and homologation?

For OEMs:

The traffic jam chauffeur (SAE level 3 & 4⁵) function would come out first on the market because it is safer to implement. The general public needs to get used to it (public acceptance). After traffic jam, the second priority use case would be **Highway Chauffeur / Pilot (SAE level 3 & 4)**. These use cases are a priority because they will be the best-selling AD features, everybody experiences traffic jams or long mileage driving trips.

Other interesting use cases for the industry could be:

Valet Parking may be convenient, perhaps easier for a POC, and less dangerous because of the limited speed, but needs too much link with the parking infrastructure, and has a very limited interest for consumers...

Low speed shuttles (SAE level 4) may become an alternative public transportation means, but today cities need high volume public transportation means.

For policy makers:

For highway use cases the priority is clear: **highway lane keeping** will be out first, then **highway pilot with lane changes**.

Another priority use case would be **Low speed shuttle in urban area at SAE level 5**, but maybe with an operator who can be outside the vehicle and able to intervene in case of emergency. The situations in an urban environment are more complex and can only be addressed at low speed because of the pedestrians. There are several possibilities of service for this use case: Delivering robots (e.g. online shopping, post, food) or public transportation.

What we will not see is **high speed on urban and rural road** because it is not currently feasible for a system to master all situations that might occur, and it is as well a big challenge for future developments.

Connectivity is challenging in mixed traffic because all vehicles would have to be equipped. Infrastructure could inform the vehicles if a road user is coming at an intersection, but it would be too expensive to cover the areas.

For research institutes:

Several opinions were given by different research institutes:

According to most of the research institutes interviewed, **Highway driving/pilot (SAE level 3 & 4)** is the use case that will be out first on the market and that should be treated in priority. Several research institutes pointed out that the SAE level 3 automated functions will not be released on the market because it is too risky for OEMs (MRM and HMI will be very difficult to put in place and avoid misuse). The **traffic jam chauffeur (SAE level 3 & 4)** function was often associated with highway pilot and could also be implemented soon.

A research institute said that **Urban driving functions (SAE level 4)** will soon become the priority as there are many complex situations that should be handled. However, during most interviews, Automated driving in an urban

⁵ According to the SAE J3016 standard from <https://www.sae.org/news/2019/01/sae-updates-j3016-automated-driving-graphic>

environment was only considered for for low speed shuttle. An urban driving function in a passenger car was considered too difficult to implement and not a priority by the majority of stakeholders interviewed. Urban driving will be quite more complicated as the complexity of the layout will be higher and the number and diversity of road users surrounding the CAD VEHICLE will increase considerably.

Interviewed research centres considered that **truck platooning** is a good start for certification because there is a market for it (due to fuel consumption and safety). The real benefit will be for the transport companies, not only for the OEMs.

Regarding the use case **Valet parking**, 3 categories were distinguished:

1. Dedicated parking only for autonomous vehicles (no human inside)
2. Shared parking (CAD vehicle and traditional vehicles)
3. Parking in a non-dedicated area (at home or in the street)

The priority for certification should be the use cases in which the safety of the occupants of the car and other users of the road is more at risk.

3.2 Benefits

This section presents the answers to the question 3 of the questionnaire : 3) What are the benefits associated to your use cases?

For OEMs:

- **Highway Chauffeur / Pilot (SAE level 3 & 4):** The advantages are a better comfort while driving, less stress; an improved safety overall (this will need to be proven by studies after launch), better traffic fluidity (also needs to be proven by studies).
- **Traffic jam chauffeur (SAE level 3 & 4):** There is an improvement of the driving comfort and a potential economic and environmental impact with a lower consumption of gas (not proven yet). Finally, traffic jam pilot greatly improves safety even though some new risks might be created.

Overall, there is a pacifying effect on the driver, and on the other cars. More peaceful driving leads to more respect of driving laws, less inattention, and will lead to less accidents, and fatalities on the road. AD functions could also allow elderly people or people with disabilities to drive longer because it will be less exhausting.

For Policy makers:

Highway Chauffeur / Pilot (SAE level 3 & 4):

- **Added comfort** is a benefit for the driver.
- With mixed traffic the effect of **traffic safety** is not so high, the main benefit for safety happens for rear end accidents.
- **Improved traffic flow** is difficult to obtain in a mixed traffic situation. The benefits on the near future will not be so high.

Low speed shuttle (SAE level 4):

- It will be useful for customers who cannot drive as an **alternative to public transport**.
- Saving driver costs
- No safety or traffic benefits for this use case, or fuel consumption (e.g. hotel have shuttle services).

The benefits for OEMs will come later, consumers need to experience the benefits first. At the beginning, CAD functions will only be for luxury cars. The OEMs have to do the first step to develop CAD vehicles even if it does not bring a lot of benefits at the beginning.

For Research institutes:

Safety is a major benefit for CAD vehicles because the machines do not make human mistakes and do not get tired

- **Highway Chauffeur / Pilot (SAE level 3 & 4):** improves the driver's comfort, reduces fatigue and stress. Safety distances will be more respected. This use case will allow to do other activities while driving like working. It will also save fuel thanks to a better energy consumption management. It will also be safer by eliminating human failure.
- **Robot taxi (SAE level5):** will improve the traffic flow, reduce pollution and accidents.
- **Valet Parking:** This use case will allow to save space and time for consumers as they do not have to find a parking space and can call back their car.
- **Truck platooning** will mainly benefit the transportation companies, not only for the OEMs. It will bring an improved operability because the driver can rest and drive longer so it increases productivity. There will be environmental benefits with fuel saving, less wind resistance. Comfort of the driver is also an advantage because the driver would be able to sleep.
- **For platooning with smaller trucks and optional/no driver:** the benefits would be to save costs and to be more efficient by using the drivers more efficiently.

3.3 Social acceptability

This section presents the answers to the question 4 of the questionnaire : 4) What do you think of the social acceptability for these use cases (accepted in 3 / 7 / 15 years)?

For OEMs:

The traffic jam chauffeur (SAE level 3 & 4) and Highway Chauffeur / Pilot (SAE level 3 & 4) should be socially accepted in the next 3 to 7 years for SAE level 3 or 4. As it is a niche market there is not many people to convince at the moment. There is a lot of communication for CAD that is made to the public that might confuse them. Social acceptance will take time because not many people are concerned by these use cases. If the CAD functions are working fine and do not cause accidents, then the public will accept them.

Overall the function will be socially accepted:

- if the driver feels safe.
- If the driver is not too confident in the system's abilities.
- If there are very few accidents and fatal accidents.

For Policy makers:

There should not be any problem with acceptance as long as the technology is safe and does not produce any accidents. As an example, hydrogen cars have a problem of acceptance because of the (potential) accidents. Social acceptance depends on how good the legislator is at rule making and the OEM at safe technology. CAD technology will be introduced step by step.

For Research institutes:

- **Highway Chauffeur / Pilot (SAE level 3 & 4) and traffic jam chauffeur:** The social acceptance is good even if it will take a few years to be fully accepted by the society. If the system is not safe enough, it will then be a high risk for the OEMs. Therefore, these functions need to be very well validated and even more than what the law (should) cover. The driver will easily rely on the system after about 5 times using it. The Highway pilot as an assistance (ADAS) is already available in many cars: this previous version of what will be a completely automated function will accelerate the acceptance of these systems in the short term. It will be possible to have automated vehicles operational in this use case in 3 years. For **Highway Chauffeur SAE level 3**, the social acceptance would be immediate but there is a higher risk of over-trusting the system and using the AD function outside the ODD.

- **Robot taxi:** the social acceptance will come later. It will be accepted if it improves the global traffic situation, demonstrations are needed to prove the safety value. No steering wheel in the vehicle can scare some people. The main challenge is to make a robot taxi behave similar to normal human driving. The goal is to work within the facility that is adapted to OEM's ODD.
- **Truck platooning** could be accepted quickly but it is not just a technical question, the legal framework has to be in place. The benefits could be seen quickly by the public so there would be a high social acceptability. Between 3 and 7 years from now it should be accepted on the market.
- Another research institute said that **truck platooning** would be easily accepted (released and accepted within 5-10 years).

3.4 Risks

This section presents the answers to the question 5 of the questionnaire : 5) What are the risks associated to your use cases? (e.g. risks on connectivity, different infrastructures...)

For OEMs:

For the **Highway use cases**, a general risk could be the loss of connectivity as well as a cyber-attack. But connectivity it is not the most critical function for this use case.

Overall, the main safety risk is the inappropriate use of the CAD function (using the system outside the ODD). The driver behaviour is critical if there is an overconfidence in the system.

Some risks will also be caused by the mixed traffic and illegal behaviours from other road users.

For Policy makers:

There should not be any specific risk because the rule will cover most of the hazardous situations.

The misuse of the function can be handled in design. Very strict rules will be put in place to minimize the misuse situations. The risk of misuse of the function is higher for the SAE level 2 than for SAE level 2.

A potential accident could be due to criminal activity for higher levels of automation. If there is a measure that guarantees cybersecurity, then the system will be harder to manipulate. Manufacturers need to be ready for cybersecurity.

For Research institutes:

- For the **highway use cases**, the risk is quite important due the high speed and mixed traffic conditions. The system needs to be able to drive under different weather conditions like snow or heavy rain. At first, the system will not be able to rely so much on communication to understand its environment, the system will only rely on its sensors. So, a risk would be a misinterpretation of a situation leading to an accident. The loss of communication and positioning are also critical. In a critical situation, a fall back is needed to reach a safe state. (e.g. park on the side of the road/ use camera system or digital map to navigate temporarily). Even if the highway conditions are quite similar in Europe, it may not be possible to use the system in other countries (Europe or global).
- **Robot taxi:** Because of the low speed of the vehicle, the main challenge comes from the pedestrians and Vulnerable Road Users (VRUs); it is important to make sure that the perception system can understand/perceive the real situation.
- **Valet Parking:** The first solution may be in a closed parking lot without humans and in a very controlled environment which will be easier to handle.
- The risks associated with **truck platooning** are linked with **positioning** (relative distance) and **V2X communication**. If you lose communication with the platoon or receive a false signal, it can be a big threat for the platoon. Cross border, multi brand and good alignment for the platooning are hard to

implement. The main risk for **positioning** is not being able to recognize the signs (speed, etc.). **Cybersecurity** is also very important for truck platooning but not treated by the research institutes interviewed. There are risks for safety because the trucks are driving close to each other (0.8 sec at 80 km/h).

The automated vehicle's capacity to adapt to the different infrastructures, between countries for example, could affect the arrival and approval of these vehicles. In any case the risk taken by the system should be acceptable.

3.5 Minimum system requirements

This section presents the answers to the question 6 of the questionnaire : 6) What are your minimum system requirements for these use cases? (e.g. Have only one camera. Mandatory 2 technologies for 2 sensors)

For OEMs:

- **Highway Chauffeur / Pilot (SAE level 3 & 4):** sensors should be able to see 360°.
- **For Highway Chauffeur (SAE level 3):** The driver's actions and availability should be monitored. Monitoring the driver's minimum capacity to take over is necessary. The SAE level 3 is more complex than level 4 because there is a higher chance of misusing the function. The access to CAD functionalities should be restricted in the vehicle design phase.

In France, the minimum system requirements are being defined in the French Safety Position Paper, that will be published by PFA (French Automotive Platform), and written by AD Safety experts from PSA Group, Renault Group, Valeo, and 2 research institutes, VEDECOM and SystemX.

For Policy makers:

It is not about sensors or technology. The requirements are given by the traffic rules (e.g. objective of no collision), the automated vehicle has to consider other road users but cannot predict all their actions. The rule maker has to fix the limit of what has to be avoided and what is the fault of other vehicles. This can be done by selecting edge scenarios that are a challenge for the CAD vehicle.

Example of edge scenarios: cut-out in front of a stationary object / object falls from a truck / wild animal, etc.

Some accidents are unavoidable. The rule maker says that CAD needs to handle a certain number of scenarios to be certified. Product liability of the manufacturer also has to be guaranteed, not only by rule maker. The OEMs have to go further than what is asked by the regulation by testing "edge test cases". The rule maker can only test challenging edge cases. Not all scenarios can be tested for certification.

A potential approach would be to select edge cases, test them, approve the vehicle and check that the OEM has tested other use cases.

For Research institutes:

The **Highway Chauffeur / Pilot (SAE level 3 & 4)** will need the following technologies:

- Cameras for lane marking and signs detection. A 360° camera perception will be recommended in case of lane change.
- Laser Scanner, however the performances are degraded in case of bad weather (e.g. Heavy Rain).
- Radar should always be combined with other technologies.
- The sensor fusion of these technologies (radar, camera, lidar) is needed and will allow redundancy to have a better safety in case of bad weather.

For **Valet Parking** in dedicated parking only for autonomous vehicles (no human inside): a laser scanner may be sufficient. In addition, ultrasonic sensors may be used. The cameras are not mandatory in case of a dedicated parking as the area is controlled.

For truck platooning, the minimum system requirements are: communication with other trucks and infrastructure, radars, (maybe cameras on the side mirrors), etc.

For Robot Taxi (SAE level 5): the minimum system requirements are: Power supply availability, Lidars, cameras, high precision positioning. Redundancy of the sensors.

In any case, it will be important to know well the sensor perception quality (that should be tested separately from the whole vehicle) and to get enough redundancy regarding perception.

3.6 Limitations of the system

This section presents the answers to the question 7 of the questionnaire : 7) What are the associated performances/limitations for the system? Ex: not working by night (ODD).

For OEMs:

Highway Chauffeur / Pilot (SAE level 3 & 4): Some environmental conditions such as rain, temperature, snow or night time can be limitations.

The main issues come from SOTIF⁶ constraints, strongly linked to the sensor performances, road infrastructures, and safety constraints. The final performance will be a compromise.

For research institutes:

- **Highway Chauffeur / Pilot (SAE level 3 & 4)**: The system may not work under severe weather conditions like heavy rain or snow). Driving at night should not be a problem.
- **Robot Taxi**: Speed limit of 30 km/h, the vehicle can drive only during the day, severe weather conditions can also be a limitation.
- **Valet Parking**: The limitations will be depending on the type of valet parking function.
- **Truck platooning**: Bad environmental conditions & certain traffic situations: low visibility, pedestrians or big animals on the road, etc.

3.7 MRM (Minimum Risk Manoeuvre) and HMI (Human-Machine Interface)

This section presents the answers to the question 8 of the questionnaire : 8) What MRM (Minimum Risk Manoeuvre) and HMI (Human-Machine Interface) do you consider for your use cases?

For OEMs:

If the driver does not respond or cannot take over, the car has to do something (e.g. activating warnings and stop on the side). It is impossible to avoid every accident (because of other road users' behaviour). The MRM would be used to do emergency manoeuvres:

- To avoid accidents caused by the EGO
- The car has to manoeuvre to avoid risky situations
- If the driver cannot take over, then the car needs to be able to reach a safe spot as waiting for the driver to respond.

For policy makers:

For SAE level 4: MRM should not be a problem, because by design the vehicle has to reach safety by itself.

For SAE level 3: It is more difficult, MRM is only needed if the driver fails to take control again.

⁶ From ISO/PAS 21448:2019 "Road vehicles- Safety of the intended functionality"
<https://www.iso.org/standard/70939.html>

Highway Chauffeur / Pilot (SAE level 3 & 4): MRM might be needed to stop on the emergency lane.

MRM should be tested on closed track because it is unsafe on open road. The best option is to include several test tracks on geofencing of the vehicle with emergency lane. The tests should not only include car road users but also motorcycles.

In Germany, it is not allowed to stop on an emergency lane unjustified (or test reasons). The traffic law would have to be adapted if testing on open road is needed. It is hard to test a vehicle on open road if it is not certified yet.

For research institutes:

- **Highway (SAE level 2):** The car should be able to stop within 10 seconds and the driver takes over quickly. There is no solution yet if the driver refuses to take control of the car.
- **Highway Chauffeur (SAE level 3):** The car should be able to stop on the side of the highway in case of danger, and then the driver can takeover.
- **Highway Pilot (SAE level 4):** The system should be able to handle a 10 to 15s driving time before a takeover. The car should then be able to drive to a safe spot in case there is no takeover.
- **Robot Taxi (SAE level 5):** The main challenge is to find how to put the vehicle in a safe situation. Because it is a level 4 or 5, the vehicle should be able to handle critical situation without the passenger's intervention.
- **Valet Parking:** There is no minimum risk manoeuvre needed. The vehicle stops as soon as there is a critical situation.
- **Truck platooning:** When opening the gap between members of the platoon, if another road user makes a cut in, the rear vehicle would start breaking.

About HMI: Having a good Human Machine Interface is also crucial to make sure that the system knows the status of the driver for overtaking (Hands in contact with the steering wheel, or eye monitoring / small talk detection / obligation to only use vehicle screen (Audi approach)). If the driver does not respond, then an alert should be given (loud information sound) to remind the driver to take over.

3.8 Road infrastructure

This section presents the answers to the question 9 of the questionnaire : 9) What kind of infrastructure/road is needed for your use cases? Do you see any change in infrastructure useful to help the implementation of these use cases?

For OEMs:

According to some of the OEMs interviewed, for the **Highway use cases**, no special infrastructure is needed. Some possible improvements for the infrastructure could be: Connectivity, Electric Vehicles (EV) chargers, potholes cancellation, lane markings with reflective paintings, High Definition (HD) Map with regular updates.

In France, the roads need to be compliant with the French road guideline T80 (i.e. dual carriage motorway with physical barrier, limited access, separated from the environment, no intersection).

For policy makers:

A general problem is that infrastructure changes are a cost for the government (e.g. clear lane marking, road maintenance, etc.). At the beginning, CAD vehicles should be able to drive without any special infrastructure. If the system cannot drive on certain roads, then it will have to hand over to the driver.

For research institutes:

- **Highway Chauffeur / Pilot (SAE level 3 & 4):** The current highway infrastructure can be used, maybe wider lines or good road markings could improve the performances of these uses cases.

- **Robot Taxi:** A special infrastructure is needed at the moment. The vehicle movements are limited to a defined area. Infrastructure needs to include high precision GPS.
- **Valet Parking:** Parking should be a dedicated area with a specific system to have a precise map from the parking and to know the free spaces. The system may be completed by signs that could be read by 3D cameras.
- **Truck platooning** is focussed on highway, not limited to a specific lane.

Existing roads could be enhanced with **communication** to send information (e.g. speed limit) to the vehicles. If we want sustainable transport, we need electrification, communication and automation.

3.9 Traffic

This section presents the answers to the question 10 of the questionnaire : 10) What kind of traffic is needed for these use cases?

For OEMs:

Traffic jam chauffeur: Only in dense traffic (limited speed), construction works can be a limitation. As an example, traffic jam can be qualified with a speed lower than 60km/h on a road with legal speed limit of 110 or 130 km/h.

Highway pilot requires a normal traffic on highway and also includes traffic jam.

For policy makers:

Highway/motorway use cases will be in normal mixed traffic.

Low speed shuttle might drive on a dedicated path (e.g. extra lane). However, it will be difficult to have dedicated lanes for CAD vehicle due to the lack of space.

For research institutes:

- **Highway Chauffeur (SAE level3):** There are no specific traffic conditions for this use case. Even in case of traffic jam, the system should be able to handle it.
- **Highway Pilot (SAE level4):** All the situations should be handled.
- **Robot Taxi:** A low traffic environment is needed.
- **Valet Parking:** Not concerned
- **Truck platooning:** Any kind of normal traffic on highway, traffic jam possible thanks to the “stop and go” function. No pedestrians or cyclists.

The traffic depends on the scenario that we would like to test.

3.10 Certification procedures and tools

This section presents the answers to the question 12 of the questionnaire : 12) What procedures and tools could be used to test your use cases?

For OEMs:

- Simulation (MiL, SiL) can be used for Driving Policy
- Driving Simulators: User Experience, HMI validation, Take-Over Requests (TOR), etc.
- Proving ground tests:
 - for repeatable and secure testing,
 - for sensor verification
 - for customer performance assessment on specific tests
- Real World Driving:
 - For sensor verification
 - For other road user acceptance evaluation
 - For customer performance synthesis on real traffic
 - For detecting unforeseeable scenarios

The best procedure would be a mix of Test Track (TT), real world verification, ghost driving and simulation (for critical manoeuvres and accidents).

For policy makers:

The point of view of **certification technical service** and **type approval** on this topic are detailed in the chapter 7 of this document “Certification/ Type approval (tools, procedures)”

For research institutes:

For the **highway** and **parking** use cases, several procedures and tools can be used:

- Scenario databases are needed to know the real traffic situations but require many kilometres driven to be realistic.
- Simulations tools are useful in addition to proving ground and open road testing.
- X in the loop: Needs the dynamics of a real car but with virtual traffic actors from simulation. X in the loop is used for proving ground or simulation.

For Robot Taxi (SAE level 5): Hardware in the loop (HIL) and software in the loop (SIL) are used to for testing. There are not many tests made at vehicle level at the moment. The requirements are defined and tested at different levels to ensure reliability and find issues as early as possible. The goal is to find a functional concept for testing before starting the tests at vehicle level.

Overall, all available tools should be used, it is not possible to only do physical testing; simulation and real-world testing have to be included as well.

Procedures for **truck platooning** certification are not clear yet; projects such as ENSEMBLE are working on this topic.

The test laboratories have their own procedures to test the use cases on their test tracks. The vehicles are equipped to record all the data of the use case (e.g. inter distance between vehicles, speeds, trajectories, acceleration, etc.)

3.11 Methodology for certification

This section presents the answers to the question 13 of the questionnaire : 13) What methodology would you like to use for certification?

For OEMs:

We need a new process that would be a mix of the three test instances (simulation, TT, open road). There are too many scenarios to be tested, so not every scenario can be tested physically. OICA’s three pillars approach⁷ is a promising approach:

- **Audit (1 day):**
 - Of the safety approach,
 - Of massive simulation,
 - Of real-world driving,
- **Proving ground test (3 days):**
 - On less than 10 scenarios,
 - To validate simulation,
 - To perform standardized strong manoeuvres like MRM, EM, etc.
 - To test blind sensors.

⁷ <http://www.unece.org/fileadmin/DAM/trans/doc/2019/wp29grva/GRVA-02-09e.pdf>

- **Real-world driving (1 or 2 hours):**
 - Something like a Driving Permit Examination,
 - No selected roads,
 - Mandatory scenarios to be done among a list (list to be defined),
 - At the limit of the ODD.

For policy makers:

For homologation: The priority is to test physically on Test Track and if it is not possible on TT (e.g. because the risk is too high), then test the vehicle on simulation (simulation will rely on OEM documentation). The manufacturer will also be audited to check how they guaranty that the simulation results are in line with the real tests. The standards: ISO 26262 and ISO PAS 21448 (SOTIF) can also be used. It is not sure that **simulation testing** could be done by the certification technical services. How many simulations would be needed is also unknown. This topic needs to be discussed between EU member states. The government will have to test specific cases but cannot test all scenarios, they will have to rely on the OEMs.

For research institutes:

Type approval procedures are part of the already existing law. Vehicles could be certified from all around Europe.

The main goal is to build a scenario database that allows to extract situations that can then be used on test tracks and simulation. Regarding the certification, it will require dedicated scenarios that cannot be on open road as they should be deterministic.

3.12 Benefits and disadvantages of testing CAD vehicles on test track, open road and simulation

This section presents the answers to the question 14 of the questionnaire : 14) What are the benefits and disadvantages of testing CAV on test track and open road vs. simulation for this use case / scenarios? How do you link test instances (proving ground, simulation, real world field test)?

For OEMs:

- **Simulation** is used for standard test cases, it can also be used in extreme cases (critical), there is a huge number of scenarios with a lot of variations, but not realistic (too perfect environment and sensor models).
- **Test track** is a controlled environment, the advantage are the repeatability of tests, the possibility to test “hard/strong” manoeuvres; the environment & sensors are real; possibility to know the driver’s feelings. But it takes a long time to prepare & test a system, very few test cases are expected.
- **Open road** is the only place where there is a real environment, a real system and a real-world high level of variability. It is possible to verify the acceptance of AD by other road users. Open road is used for final verification to control that the system works under certain parameters. the inconvenient part is that open road testing is time consuming, not repeatable, and there is no control over the environment (tests are done under different weather/traffic conditions).

Testing should be simulation driven. Tests on proving ground should be focused on specific test cases to correlate simulation & physical tests. Open road testing should be a way to validate the overall behaviour of the vehicle, and to give confidence in simulation and tests on test tracks results.

For the highway use cases, the experimentations are done mostly on open road, partly on test track.

For policy makers:

- **Simulation:** can check a much bigger variety of scenarios. The risk is the lack of realism of what is simulated. The technical services will have to rely on OEMs for simulations.
- **Test Track:** gives physical proof that the system works.

- **Open road:** more scenarios can be discovered. The disadvantage is that the test is not objective and cannot be reproduced with the same parameters.

It is very hard to test a specific scenario on open road because the test environment changes from one test to another.

A good methodology could be to add some real-world field tests to have a good overview from the scenarios.

For research institutes:

- **Simulation** has the advantage of testing a lot of scenarios in a short time with a low cost. Simulation can test much more cases than physical testing. It is also possible to test hazardous scenarios that cannot be tested on track. The problem of simulation is the difficulty to test the perception of the sensors (possible to test the system but not the sensor) that can have a big influence in the final performances of the system. If the radar detects the other car, 0.1s before or after that could change the result. The other problem of simulation is the disparity between the different softwares and methods.
- **Test Track** has the advantage of being more realistic in terms of dynamics, but this solution is more expensive and takes longer time. Test track is good for testing well defined scenarios. At component level, it is possible to add errors to the electronics and check how the system reacts to ensure safety. Simulation as well as test track are risk free as there are no unintended accidents and other people are not exposed to the risks.
- **Open road testing** has the advantage of being a truly realistic environment. Open road tests can be used for verification purposes. Testing V2X communication and positioning is possible. It can also be used for validating functional safety (SOTIF), find unknown scenarios. The disadvantage is that we cannot prove that the vehicle is safe enough just with open road testing because it would require to drive too many kilometres. Open road testing does not allow to test scenarios and makes it hard to have deterministic behaviour.

Consumer testing is only focusing on proving ground testing at the moment. Simulation will be implemented in the future because the number of scenarios with CAD will increase and will not be doable only on test track. The future development of consumer testing will focus on how to separate scenarios between proving ground and simulation. Open road is not considered by consumer testing, because it is unpredictable, and repeatability is necessary.

The best approach for testing safety would be a mix of the three test instances in order to get a full validation. Some people are working on the link between test instances. The test instances are defined for each requirement.

4 Safety Assessment and Safety-Case

This chapter introduces the survey and interviews of experts for the topic of safety assessment and safety case. Each sub-chapter represents a topic of discussion addressed in the questionnaire. The needs expressed are organised between each type of stakeholder that were interviewed. The stakeholders interviewed on this topic are the same that were interviewed for the topic of use-cases and scenarios and are presented in the **FIGURE 1 TYPE OF STAKEHOLDERS – USE CASES AND SCENARIOS**. For the purpose of the interviews, the aim of the questionnaire is to identify the requirements of different types of industry stakeholders on the main risks and safety requirements linked to CAD. The questionnaire used for this topic of interview is available in the annex 3 of this report. The key stakeholders' needs expressed in these interviews will be synthesized in the chapter 10.2 of this report.

4.1 Main hazards and risks for the safety of a CAD vehicles

This section presents the answers to the question 1 of the questionnaire : 1)What are the new risks/hazards introduced by Connected and Automated Vehicles (for any use case at SAE level 3, 4 & 5)?

For OEMs:

The main risk for SAE level 3 is that the CAD function is not well understood and misused. This misuse could lead to fatal accidents and injuries.

Overall, CAD vehicles are more safe than traditional vehicles but are also bringing new risks and critical situations. Some new risks could be during the takeover phase or if a bug happens in the system.

For Policy makers:

The biggest challenge is that the vehicle needs to master all situations in the ODD if the driver is not available to take over right away. There is an infinite number of scenarios and situations because of small variations of parameters between two similar situations.

In the end, some situations cannot be mastered by the vehicle (e.g. someone throwing a stone from a bridge / or a motorcycle stopped on the road) as these are very rare events.

A decision has to be made: do we want to accept these risks? The solution is to find a balance / compromise between possible new risk created against the benefits brought by this new technology.

Society can accept human failure but does not accept machine failure at the same level. The car should not harm anyone. The public has to experience that machine is better than human before accepting mistakes from car.

For Research institutes:

Overall, the risks are new because CAD is a new technology. These new risks are different for each autonomy level. For example, the interactions with the human inside the car are critical at SAE level 3 but less at SAE level 4 and almost not a problem at SAE level 5. For this reason, it is not sure that the SAE level 3 is feasible.

For the vehicles that are not fully autonomous, the main hazards are happening when handing the control from driver to the machine. When the CAD vehicle encounters a complex situation, it cannot improvise like a human driver, it is very difficult for sensors to identify all potential hazards. A SAE level 5 vehicle has to handle all situations, but for a SAE level 3, the interactions Human-Machine are critical. A major risk is that the CAD vehicle is not able to react to hazardous situations as well as an attentive driver when facing a situation that is not present in the scenario database.

The CAD will always follow the traffic rules, and this can be a hazard in some area.

In an urban area, the main risk is to have cars moving too slowly to safely face all the situations (like interaction with pedestrians, bicycles, etc.). Therefore, people may not see the advantage to use CAD. Sensor limitation is also an important risk and challenge for CAD vehicles.

Another risk for safety is the introduction of Artificial intelligence (AI) in the car. The AI needs to have a good reasoning. It is difficult to control the future software version of the vehicle once the vehicle is approved. In order to determine that the vehicle is safe enough with the new software, the software updates need to be controlled for a vehicle that changes from one level to another with an update.

4.2 Qualitative and quantitative safety objectives

This section presents the answers to the question 2 of the questionnaire : 2) What are your objectives for testing CAD safety?

For OEMs:

The objectives depend on the type of function used, for which SAE level and for which safety criteria. These objectives will be verified by audit, by simulation or by testing on PG. In France, some qualitative rules have been defined by the PFA Safety Position Paper. The quantitative and qualitative targets could also come from an ethic commission such as “at least as good as...”.

Qualitative objectives exist today, but it is not easy to translate them into **quantitative objectives**. To deal with scenarios that can be predicted by a human, we need to be able to quantify them. A human model is not easy to define because there is no reference for the human behaviour. Furthermore, it is not easy to determine if an accident is avoidable or not.

For Policy makers:

Quantitative objectives: Collision-free traffic

Qualitative objectives: Duty of care to avoid accidents even if it is caused by a mistake from a third party. The vehicle needs to be able to make evasive manoeuvres (capability to avoid others’ mistakes to a certain degree, this limit needs to be fixed by the legislator)

For Research institutes:

Qualitative objectives: Improve safety of CAD vehicles.

Quantitative objectives: Assess the capabilities of these systems to react to a common dangerous situation that can be found during the use of these functions. Being able at the end to compare and evaluate different similar systems. Quantitative objectives are difficult to define. They may be possible at OEM level (design, internal validation, etc.)

In Spain, the overall safety objectives are defined by the Spanish road authority (quantitative objective could be zero accidents). The requirements from the “Instrucción 15.v/113” are more qualitative than quantitative. This is because the tests are supposed to be performed in a very restricted area considering other measures.

Zero accidents may be hard to achieve as there will always be unforeseen situations. The automated driving functions should be compared to human driving. The reference human model approach is handled in several projects like PEGASUS. When this driver model is available, it will be used in the testing toolchain.

For **truck platooning on highway**, the main risks are well known because of previous projects, so it is easier to model safety than for other use cases. It is necessary to show the differences in safety with traditional truck driving and to prove that truck platooning is safer. However, it is difficult to show that it is safer when traditional truck driving is already quite safe, and it would require tests over 1 million kilometres. The main goal of truck platooning is efficiency, not safety. However, safety shall not be compromised.

For **consumer testing**, the safety objectives only concern the level 2 function at the moment; there are quantitative and qualitative objectives:

- **Quantitative:** Define a scenario based on accidentology studies (e.g. How many times is the system able to avoid the accident?)

- **Qualitative:** There is a focus on HMI (Details of the CAD function in the manual / how to activate the function / How to alert the driver / design an emergency alert for activating function outside the ODD). For future level 3, the system needs to be able to safely avoid the accident.

4.3 The scenario-based approach

This section presents the answers to the question 3 of the questionnaire : 3) Do you think the scenario-based approach should be used to validate CAD safety? Why?

For OEMs:

The scenario-based approach should be used to validate CAD safety. It is not a safety-requirement based, but rather a safety risk analysis-based approach.

Assessing Safety with the scenario-based approach is new from CAD. ISO standards and scenario-based approach are both necessary. Testing scenarios is a minimum requirement to ensure that the system is safe.

The most important safety points are the SOTIF ones (PAS SOTIF 21448 and its evolutions). The SOTIF is scenario-based.

For Policy makers:

There is an infinite number of scenarios that can be tested, not everything can be tested on test track, so it is necessary to make a selection of the most relevant scenarios to test.

A scenario database is needed to collect traffic situations. then this database will be used as a base to choose the relevant scenarios to test CAD vehicles in the future. The scenarios to test can be randomly picked (e.g. 10000 scenarios in the database, 20 are tested) so it is ensured that the OEM has developed a safe system.

It is important to learn about what are the challenging and important scenarios. Scenario selection is essential for more complex automation.

Policy makers cannot rely on databases that are made only by OEMs, a neutral database is needed for type approval. We need to be sure that the scenarios in the database are representative of the real traffic situations. In the end the database needs to be handled by governments. The database used should be governmental (national or European)

A module will be needed on top of the database to simulate if the criteria are met for each scenario tested to prove that the vehicle is safe enough.

For Research institutes:

The Scenario based approach is used for simulation in ADAS and CAD testing. Some research institutes said that there is no need for a different approach.

The scenario-based approach is considered for the overall systems tests. The unitary tests on sensors and components may use another approach.

Consumer testing is always validating safety based on scenarios.

The Ideal approach would be the scenario-based approach with all the use cases. But this approach can be limited when there is not enough data available for some specific use cases (such as truck platooning) where experimentations on open road are limited. Realistically, the scenario database is too limited. The engineers working on the use case are defining the scenarios that are wanted. The scenario-based approach is a good starting point to evaluate the performances and safety of those systems. Other methods such as counting the number of requested interventions of the driver during a circuit in open road could also be a good approach.

4.4 Scenarios to test for CAD safety

This section presents the answers to the question 4 of the questionnaire : 4) What are the scenarios for your use cases to assess the safety of a CAD?

For OEMs:

All scenarios where manoeuvres are involved (e.g. cut in, etc.) have to be tested (e.g. scenarios with interactions with other vehicles).

The takeover request scenarios need to be tested in a different way. These scenarios are tested in simulation at the moment, but it is still in Research & Development phase. It is not sure how to test them for homologation. Guidelines for homologation will have to be defined.

The French OEMs are defining a library of functional & logical scenarios to consider for safety evaluation. These scenarios have to meet some requirements:

- **Legitim:** Its origin is known. Extracted from well-known database.
- **Recognized:** Chosen by experts
- **Shared:** e.g. agreement of several OEMs, Suppliers, Laboratories
- **Covering:** Relevant scenarios for a particular ODD are gathered here.

The goal is not to define a list of concrete scenarios to be passed for certification, but a list of functional or logical scenarios with their variabilities to cover the ODD.

For Policy makers:

All scenarios will have to be tested. Several categories of functions should be tested on Test Track (e.g. HMI, failure warning, transition phase, enough time for driver to takeover, etc.). Edge-cases will also have to be tested. The vehicles will have to be able to handle critical situation (e.g. cut in, braking, etc.)

For easy use cases, it is not necessary to have a database, the critical scenarios can be defined just by thinking. Then the regulation can be adjusted over time by trial and error.

For lower speed use cases, we need to test a scenario where someone (object) is on the road and has to stop within a certain time.

For more complex use cases, much more scenarios will have to be tested and a database is necessary. The scenario database used will be able to distinguish the different use cases and autonomy level.

Some scenarios are too complex for the car still and cannot be handled (e.g. cut in then braking/ front vehicle cut out for obstacle).

First, a lot of traffic situations have to be observed (with FOTs, cameras, drones, etc.), need to put CAD vehicle on the road and observe where accidents occur. Then the representativity of the accidents for the country can be calculated. The scenarios can be categorised between normal driving and special case. This process might last 10 to 20 years to have reliable data. There will be a learning phase. Mixed traffic will generate new accidents / risks. These new risks will have to be low enough to be accepted by the public.

For Research institutes:

- **For Highway Chauffeur / Pilot (SAE level 3 & 4):** Many projects on this topic are still running which cannot bring a precise list. However, the challenger approach is often taken into consideration. The ego vehicle needs then to perform an action depending on this challenger. Many different possibilities are then offered. This approach may be extended for urban area with more situations. The possible scenarios for this use case are: Assessment of emergency braking; Stationary objects on the road; braking object in front of the ego; Object moving slower; Emergency steering; Cut in/Cut out; stationary/moving and braking forward traffic; lane keeping in strong curves; reduction of lane numbers; insertion, etc.

- **For traffic jam chauffeur (SAE level 3 & 4):** Entering traffic jam / leaving traffic jam/ etc.
- **For Robot Taxi:** The definition of scenarios is more complex because it is SAE level 5. The vehicle will have to deal with pedestrians (unpredictable behaviour). Scenarios focussing on pedestrians, at low speed (30km/h). Cyclists and other vulnerable road users are not yet considered in the scenarios.
- **For truck platooning,** there are 5 main categories of scenarios to ensure safety (according to the ENSEMBLE project⁸).
 - Platoon formation
 - Engaging to platoon
 - Platooning
 - Disengage platoon
 - Other
- **For Valet Parking:** the scenarios will involve people moving around the cars (especially from behind) and communication problems.

4.5 Testing procedures and tools for CAD safety

This section presents the answers to the question 5 of the questionnaire : 5) What testing procedures and tools are needed for assessing the safety of a CAD?

For OEMs:

Safety reassurance can be assessed by driving in normal conditions. The **safety benefit** assessment will be quantified by comparing the accidentology statistics. The **tools** that can be used for testing safety are **test track, simulation** and **open road** testing.

For the French OEMs, two kind of tools can be used to assess CAD safety depending if it is before or after the start of sales (SOS):

Before sales:

- V&V state of the art processes shall be used.
- All XiL tools (including simulation i.e. MiL and SiL), Vehicle Testing on Proving Ground and Real-World Driving.
- Pass/fail criteria needs to be defined.

After Sale:

The idea of “continuous validation” seems widely shared, so the process of safety improvement will continue, by detecting interesting safety issues, analyzing them, to update the vehicles.

A minimum number of triggering events of scenarios shall be analysed, shared, and shall fill the scenario library for each new scenario found.

For Research institutes:

It is not possible to test everything on Test Track, we need to combine test track with simulation to cover all scenarios and to prove that the system is safe. The testing procedure for process is the SOTIF.

Testing procedure for components:

- SIL
- Test benches

⁸https://platooningensemble.eu/storage/uploads/documents/2019/02/11/ENSEMBLE-D2.2---Use-Cases-and-platooning-levels_disclaimer.pdf

- Post processing tools to process data from FOT
- Data logging system able to process a lot of data.

Testing procedure for proving ground:

- Positioning tools connected to GPS
- Tools connected to infrastructure (not currently used)

Tool chain: Redundant sensor are necessary to understand the environment. First, an **assessment on the architecture** has to be done, then **simulation** and finally **physical tests**. All test instances are relevant to build up a safety case. ISO 26262 can also be used.

For certification and consumer testing: The procedure for simulation is a challenge, it is important to guarantee that EuroNCAP and road authority get the simulation output from the manufacturers.

4.6 Methodology for assessing CAD safety

This section presents the answers to the question 6 of the questionnaire : 6) What methodology are you using for assessing the safety of a CAD? How to prove that it is enough? Using the SOTIF (ISO PAS 21448)?

For OEMs:

The methodology for assessing safety should come from the scenario database. The relation between scenarios and test instances has to be established. The scenarios will be classified whether they are within the ODD or not. If the scenario database is not enough to prove that the vehicle is safe, then the SOTIF can be used.

For other OEMs, the compliance to ISO 21448 seems mandatory. Continuous improvement after the start of sales is also needed to ensure safety whatever the changes (road infrastructures, traffic rules, etc.).

For Policy makers:

For homologation: The priority is to test physically on Test Track, if not possible (e.g. because the risk is too high), then test the vehicle on simulation (simulation will rely on OEM documentation). The manufacturer will also be audited to check how they guaranty that the simulation results are in line with the real tests. The standards: ISO 26262 and ISO PAS 21448 (SOTIF) can also be used. It is not sure that **simulation testing** could be done by the certification technical services. How many simulations would be needed is also unknown. This topic needs to be discussed between EU member states. The government will have to test specific cases but cannot test all scenarios, they will have to rely on the OEMs.

Is the methodology enough: this question is not answered technically but by society, society will decide if the risk is acceptable. At the moment, the aim is collision free traffic & duty of care. In the end we cannot give a figure for accepted risk by society. The legislator will not give a figure, the goal is to do the best with expert knowledge collected (e.g. from EuroNCAP).

For Research institutes:

The methodology should follow the functional safety process, making sure that the function is safe (electronics) by using ISO 26262. ISO PAS 21448 is not enough for assessing the safety of the whole vehicle. It can be used for SAE level 1&2 functionalities. For a vehicle to be safe, it is necessary to assess all the possible situations that the car can encounter.

A lot of tests are performed first in simulation. Then it is possible to define criteria to choose which test can be used for proving ground. Finally, real world test can be used to ensure that the system works perfectly and is safe.

Regarding the OEMs, the rules and methodology will be fixed by the road authorities (e.g. follow SOTIF is compulsory for OEMs). The OEM needs to make sure that the software and AI are safe by design. The reasoning of the system needs to be provided by OEMs for certification and consumer testing.

Consumer testing is not assessing CAD at the moment, starts from accidentology and finds the most critical situation. The focus is on scenarios. The methodology is focussing on evaluating if there is an impact or no impact in the scenarios proposed for the use case.

4.7 Data to collect for CAD safety

This section presents the answers to the question 7 of the questionnaire : 7) What kind of data can be collected for the safety of CAD? Is a Black Box needed?

For OEMs:

Collecting **over the air data** would be good. But it will be difficult in Europe because of Data collection & privacy concerns. It will be difficult to collect **data on near misses** apart from OEMs. **Event Data Recorder (EDR)** can be collected as well. **Accident data** could also be collected for police reports, so that accident can be reconstructed more precisely. A **DSSAD** (Data Storage System for Automated Driving) will be mandatory in AD vehicles to identify who was driving in case of accident. Functional and Logical scenarios can be collected to feed a common scenario library.

For Policy makers:

We need data on accidents, near-misses and normal driving. These data can be collected through a black box but also from FOTs. The purpose of the black box for CAD vehicles at the beginning is to help to know who is responsible in case of an accident.

For Research institutes:

Data collection should be done for the design before the car is released. Many data are needed (sensor data, HMI data, localization data, etc.).

- Highway Chauffeur / Pilot (SAE level 3 & 4): Many data are required due to the speed and the environment. (speed, position, status of the surroundings, status of all relevant systems in the vehicle, etc.)
- Valet Parking: Due to lower risk, few data will be needed.

Data collection would be needed to determine who is responsible in case of an accident. Which data would be needed is a political question, not a technical one. As CAD is developed by OEMs, they will need data from vehicle and from the driver, sensors, algorithms, driver, control algorithm.

Collecting over the air data could be a good solution to assess the safety functions but will be very challenging due to GDPR problems.

For the STREETWISE project: Being able to rebuild the scenario and replicate it is important. Raw sensor data cannot be used, but instead post-processing data that are enough to recognise the scenario.

For truck platooning, we need to collect the data to know how people react to the platoon (e.g. how is a cut in done in between a platoon?). In any case, we cannot rely only on predefined scenarios, unknown scenarios will be encountered.

4.8 Data from Field Operation Tests

This section presents the answers to the question 8 of the questionnaire : 8) What data from Field Operational Tests can be collected for improving the CAD safety?

For OEMs:

All the **data from near misses** that does not exist in accidentology databases should be collected.

- Accidents

- All the data from near-misses / near-crashes that does not exist in accidentology databases could be collected:
 - longitudinal deceleration > threshold
 - steering wheel speed > threshold
 - brake pressure > threshold
 - very low TTC < 1s or 0,8s
 - Very low TIV < 0,5s
 - E.g. press button on a specific vehicle fleet.
- Other interesting safety event
 - E.g. press button on a specific vehicle fleet.

In France, triggers are currently under definition, and improvement, by LAB⁹.

For Policy makers:

Relevant data could be collected for accidents, near-misses and normal driving situations to fill a scenario database.

There is a clear liability of driver for level 1 and 2.

For SAE level 3: the role is shifted from driver to machine, the driver only has to be here to takeover if the machine needs it and there is a minimum time allowed to take over. From activation to deactivation, the machine is responsible (until the end of the transition phase). It's important to collect data from the transition phase in the black box.

For Research institutes:

FOTs are very important for **sensor perception**, because they are more affected by environmental condition. Useful data to collect from FOTs can be driver behaviour and HMI. Depending on the autonomy level, the driver is part of the scenario or not.

All the different data coming from the 6-layer scenario format will be used for the safety of CAD vehicles. This includes a 360° view, lane marking, signs, etc.

For Highway Chauffeur (SAE level 3), a normal test driver cannot be used. The CAD function needs to be monitored by a safety driver to avoid big accidents (e.g. Uber accident).

4.9 Current standards and regulations for testing CAD Safety

This section presents the answers to the question 9 of the questionnaire : 9) What are the current standards and regulations to take into account for the validation of CAD Safety?

National legislation

- In **Belgium**, several authorities need to give their permission in order to experiment on open road. There is no dedicated law, the requests are treated case by case.
- Some discussions on the topic of CAD are being carried on at UNECE with **NHTSA (U.S.)** and **JAMA (Japan)**
- Some laws exist in **Germany** for SAE levels 3 & 4.
- For Highway (SAE level 3): **Spain** is changing the law. Like most countries in Europe, a special approval is needed for experimentation. An intensive testing with driver monitoring is needed. Spanish regulation: Instruction 15V -113 - Authorization to conduct tests or research trials of automated vehicles on roads open to general traffic.

⁹ French Laboratory of Accidentology and Biomechanics

- In **Sweden**: there is a regulation for testing CAD vehicles, it is possible to get a permit to test on public road. A safety-case needs to be built to show the authorities the reason of the test. Safety tests cannot be the purpose of open road testing. There is always a risk of encountering an unknown and unexpected situation on open road. The risk is never foreseeable on public roads but must be acceptable.
- In the **Netherlands**: CAD testing is based on the current state (SAE level 2). CAD testing is still in a learning phase. some exemptions are made for testing on open road.

A compilation of all the different license exemption procedures existing in Europe have been done in the deliverable 3.8 of the CARTRE project¹⁰.

International legislation

Legislation always comes after the technology development. Now the focus is on individual testing, Cybersecurity and over the air update for SAE level 2 and 3 vehicles. There is no regulation for higher autonomy SAE level at the moment.

For International legislation, nothing exists yet for SAE level 3+. The new regulation should be finished in Geneva by 2020 (for lane keeping). Motorway pilot should be ready two years later. Regulation for low speed urban use cases might be up to national legislation.

European regulation: Draft to review the General Safety regulation: Amending Regulation (EU) 2018/858 and repealing Regulations (EC) No 78/2009, (EC) No 79/2009 and (EC) No 661/2009

The regulation 79 concerning the approval of vehicles with regard to steering equipment is being adapted for new functionality of ADAS.

At the moment, European regulation is limited and not always appropriate, it needs to be developed in a sustainable way.

Standards:

- ISO 26262 for functional safety
- ISO 21448 for SOTIF
- ISO 21434 for Cyber-security
- ISO TC22 SC33 WG9 on AD Test Scenarios
- WP.29 – GRVA regulation by 03/2020 for Automated Lane Keeping System (ALKS) SAE level 3-4 on highway without lane change.
- Article 20 amendment in 02/2019 for AD type approval.
- Euro NCAP 2018 communication on SAE level 2 vehicles: performance & cooperation
- ISO / TC22 / SC33 / WG9 for standards AD critical scenario (leader: China-CATARC) started in 2018

Some concerns about standards on functional safety have been expressed: ISO 26262 & ISO PAS 21448. These ISO standards for active safety are adapted to ADAS but not for automated vehicle (SAE level 3 and more).

State of the art:

- Miguel Perez & al. “Performance of basic kinematic thresholds in the identification of crash and near-crash events within naturalistic driving data” - Accident Analysis and Prevention-2017
- Eric THORN, Shawn KIMMEL, Michelle CHAKA, “A Framework for Automated Driving System Testable Cases and Scenarios”, DOT HS 812623, September 2018
- NHTSA Precrashes scenarios

¹⁰ Coordination of Automated Road Transport Deployment for Europe (CARTRE): D.3.8: “Guidance on National Testing Regulations”

- Lucie Juste, Laurette Guyonvarc'h, Arwan Lecuyer, « Naturalistic data for ADAS validation », SIA Simulation Congress, March 2019
- French Safety Position Paper published by PFA.

4.10 What to change first in the legislation?

This section presents the answers to the question 10 of the questionnaire : 10) What to change first in the legislation to guarantee the safety of CAD (connectivity with infrastructure /cyber security ...)?

For OEMs:

Harmonisation of rules is important. The driving rules and infrastructures should be harmonised in Europe to facilitate automated driving.

Standardization could help about:

- Road infrastructures (traffic signs, lane markings, etc.)
- driving rules in Europe
- Take Over Procedures
- HMI for taking over, and particularly for quick take over
- Deceleration level for MRM / EM, etc.
- Minimum inter-distance

For Policy makers:

The legislation is on the way, every issue is being tackled in working groups. Rulemaking is a slow process, but in the end the public expects no accidents when the CAD vehicle is on the road.

A topic that needs to be discussed for the new regulation is: what is the level of duty of care of CAD vehicles that should be fulfilled (e.g. should override be allowed for level 3 and up?).

Governments want to see CAD vehicles on their roads so there is pressure behind the discussions.

For Research institutes:

Gaps are hard to define for a technology that is not out already. Before the deployment of the CAD vehicle on the market, other aspects than vehicle testing will need to be regulated regarding the inspection and the driver (e.g. driving license).

The priority is to regulate lower level of autonomy first as well as the functionalities with high level of automation but not the level 5 vehicles because the technology is not ready yet.

The UNECE can specify general requirements on CAD. It is important to define what you consider as the driver. Even if the driver does not have to be on board, someone still has to be considered as a driver for legal purposes. There are some discussions made in Geneva about the responsibility that would move away from the driver at higher level. These discussions are a first step for solving the liability issue, but the topic still needs to be developed.

Some countries will be reluctant to accept a certification from another country, certification has to be done at European level. The regulation 79 on the approval of vehicles with regard to steering equipment is not enough for CAD certification.

It is hard to trust communication (connectivity). A legislation for infrastructure connectivity is needed. This legislation is needed for the validation to ensure it is compliant (in case infrastructure is damaged for example).

Other gaps in the legislation could be about:

- Changes in the infrastructure

- Cyber-security
- Privacy of data: What data should be logged?
- Artificial Intelligence: We need to ensure that it is safe. AI changing overtime will not be accepted for certification. It is more likely that the collected data will be used for future improvement by the OEMs.
- Software update: Every software update will need to be approved before release.

5 Testing

This chapter introduces the survey and interviews of experts in the field of testing. Therefore, first the structure and content of the questionnaire is introduced. After that, the results are presented. Testing is a key topic in the HEADSTART project. To create a harmonized and generally accepted methodology for testing, not only an analysis of state of the art has to take place, but also surveys and interviews with experts. This ensures that the project is aligned with current activities of stakeholders in the field of testing. The results collected in this deliverable can and will be used in the following work packages.

5.1 Structure and Content of the Questionnaire

The purpose of this questionnaire is to analyse the current situation of the market in the field of testing by interviewing relevant stakeholders. The questionnaire shall not only be utilized for face-to-face interviews, but also for online surveys. Thus, enabling the HEADSTART project to collect stakeholders' use cases and needs for following tasks, like the definition of an overall methodology.

The questionnaire is structured as follows. The first part of the questions sheds light on the background and capabilities regarding testing of the interviewee. The second part focuses on the methodology and types of testing. The following questions were utilized:

1. How do you position yourself, what category of stakeholder? (e.g. OEM, Consumer Assessment, Research Institutes)
2. What testing capabilities do you support? (e.g. Virtual Simulations, Proving Grounds, Field Operational Tests)
3. What equipment do you use on proving grounds?
4. What proving ground environment (ODD) do you have?
5. Further capabilities for proving grounds?
6. On what SAE level do you test?
7. What types of tests do you conduct? (ODD and types like performance, validation, safety assurance)
8. What tools/toolchain do you utilize?
9. Do you conduct tests regarding Cyber-Security, Positioning or Communication?
10. If (9) yes → How do you test these technologies?
11. What methodology do you use to test?
12. Do you use different methodologies for proving grounds and simulations?
13. How do you allocate scenarios between simulation, proving ground and field test?
14. What types of tests would you like to conduct for Type Approval and Certification?
15. Do you have specific tests for truck platooning?
16. If (15) yes → What types of tests do you conduct/How do you test?

All questions were kept open so that the interviewee could add further information and thereby extend the questionnaire. The results of the questionnaire on the topic of testing will be presented in the next section.

5.2 Results of the Survey and Interviews

In this section, the results of the introduced survey are presented. In figure 3 the precentral distribution of the stakeholders is shown. It can be seen that the majority of respondents are research institutes.

FIGURE 2 TYPE OF STAKEHOLDERS – TESTING

All interviewed participants support simulations and a driving simulator as testing capabilities, 75% of which even support proving ground, FOT and NDS testing. This is shown in figure 4.

FIGURE 3 TESTING CAPABILITIES

The main SAE levels on which the stakeholders conduct tests are levels 2 and 3. The results are shown in figure 5, however, just the main SAE testing levels are shown.

FIGURE 4 MAIN SAE TESTING LEVEL

In figure 6 the main types of tests which are conducted by the interviewees are presented. Most tests are conducted for performance and validation of automated driving functions.

FIGURE 5 TYPES OF TESTS

Nearly all stakeholders conduct tests for the three KETs, Positioning, Communication and Cyber-Security. For truck platooning the different scenarios are tested by the interviewees. Especially, the entrance of a truck in a platoon stands out. The results can be seen in figure 7.

FIGURE 6 TRUCK PLATOONING

All stakeholders who support proving ground capabilities, also support all listed types of equipment, ODDs and capabilities like traffic lights, lane markings or traffic signs. The methodology for testing is mostly based on protocols like EuroNCAP, but also highly depends on the clients needs. Overall, the general methodology for proving ground testing and simulations is the same. The allocation of scenarios between the different testing possibilities is based on the criticality of the scenario, the clients needs and the maturity of the system.

6 Certification/ Type approval (tools, procedures)

A questionnaire for identifying the type approval needs for testing, validation and certification of CAD functions has been carried out with relevant Technical Services and Type Approval Authorities, international organisations and research organisations. Some of the partners interviewed are already members of the consortium, but their inputs have also been considered for this analysis due to their expertise and background experience.

6.1 Structure and Content of the Questionnaire

The questionnaire comprises 8 open questions that address different topics discussed in the working groups of the UNECE and the EC as well as other challenges that regulatory bodies might face in the near future. The idea of addressing these open questions is to let the interviewee focus their answer on what they consider more relevant instead of making them choose between different options.

The full questionnaire can be found in the Annex 1 Questionnaire on Type Approval.

The following figure shows the category of the stakeholders interviewed in this case.

FIGURE 7 TYPE OF STAKEHOLDERS – CERTIFICATION/ TYPE APPROVAL

In parallel to this personalized survey, the questionnaire has been uploaded on the project website to collect input from other interested people. In this case, it will be possible to get the opinion from other stakeholders. The information coming from the online survey will be compiled at a later stage of the project, in an updated release of this deliverable.

6.2 Results of the Survey and Interviews

As a result of these activities, a wide point of view on the current gaps and the foreseen steps of the automated vehicle certification has been obtained. The key messages extracted from the questionnaire are summarized below:

- Incoming UNECE Regulations on Cyber Security and Over the Air Software will take an important paper in autonomous driving. Moreover, the WP.29 (World Forum of Harmonization of Vehicle Regulations), by the hand of its subsidiary Working Party GRVA (Working party on Automated/Autonomous and Connected Vehicles), is currently setting a new structure in order to focus on all the activities related to safety and security of vehicle automation and connectivity. Apart from the current topics, there are other relevant topics that might be addressed like Artificial Intelligence or HMI.
- The new framework regulation (EU) 2018/858¹¹ on the approval and market surveillance of motor vehicles, further develops an article with the procedure for exemptions for new technologies or new concepts, which already existed in Directive 2007/46/EC. This article, Article 39, sets out a starting point for HEADSTART project, which could complement this by defining a harmonized procedure for testing and validation of new autonomous systems for vehicles.

¹¹ Regulation (EU) 2018/858 available on: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32018R0858&from=es>

- Also early this year, in April 2019, the European Parliament approved a draft for reviewing the General Safety Regulation¹². The draft shall be taken into account, as it defines the future of the road vehicles during the following years. With regard to automated vehicles, the regulation agrees that these new technologies will gradually be taking over tasks of the driver, and may be able to reduce fatalities since more than 90 % of road accidents are estimated to result from human errors.
- Nowadays, technology is ready to introduce Level 3 vehicles on the road. However, the biggest challenge is how to establish a legal framework (also national or regional) to evaluate the safety and security of these systems.
- The International Organization of Motor Vehicle Manufacturers (OICA) has proposed a new concept for Certification based on three main pillars: Audit and Assessment, Physical Certification Tests and Real World Test Drive. It is expected that HEADSTART will provide recommendations and methodologies that will help to validate the safety aspects of the vehicle systems. It is also considered such as utilising computer simulations or virtual testing techniques to complement the safety assessments. Regarding technical services, it is important to pay attention to the testing methodology, its quality and reproducibility as well as the results reliability.
- Along all the interviews it can be concluded that it is important to define a clear distinction between virtual testing, testing on closed proving grounds and open roads, and establishing a methodology for each of them, looking for validation and type approval of automated vehicles.
- The harmonization of the procedure similar to the OBD testing emissions could be a good idea for this project. Even so, they are different subjects, and the safety validation with testing procedures is already one of the objectives in the project.
- Another challenge that the certification will face is the assessment of the vehicles and compliance of the systems during the whole life-cycle. For this reason, it is important to keep the current vehicle inspections through the Periodic Technical Inspection (PTI), but new inspection methods must be defined in order to ensure the compliance of the electronic systems and check software versions in case of software updates. Specific data from the manufacturer will be needed for the specific authorities.

During the workshop on Consumer Testing held in Eindhoven on 12 June 2019, some discussions about Type Approval came out. A specific question addressing the future of the Type Approval methodology was addressed and some discussions around this topic took place. The outcomes of the discussions are summarized below:

- From the manufacturer (and systems/supplier) point of view, it is quite clear that some of the validations will have to be done by assessment or audit.
- Also, it was agreed that, at some point, the vehicle will have to pass some testing in the real world. For this reason, the concept of the Vehicle Driving License Framework (VDLF) presented by the RDW at the ESV conference is well perceived. It was agreed that it will never be possible to completely replicate the real world driving through simulations or track testing. And the introduction of the aleatory aspect in the homologation process is seen as very positive.
- In general, test track testing was generally accepted but as a complement of simulations and real world testing, not as a main pillar for the homologation process.

The overall impression when interviewing the stakeholders is that every player involved in the Type Approval process has its own needs or wishes. For this reason, it will be difficult to fulfil all the expectations, but a

¹² Proposal for amendments of Regulation (EU) 2918/858 available on: http://www.europarl.europa.eu/doceo/document/A-8-2019-0151-AM-110-110_EN.pdf?redirect

compromise solution will have to come out. The positive aspect is that in the working groups of the UNECE, all the different stakeholders are represented (Members States, manufacturers/suppliers organisations, experts from the industry, etc.), so this compromise solution could be achieved at some point.

7 Consumer testing

The HEADSTART project will define testing and validation procedures of Connected and Automated Driving (CAD) functions including its key enabling technologies (i.e. communications, cyber-security, positioning).

Consumer testing represents a relevant final user of this methodology and a questionnaire dedicated to the current relevant topic has been developed.

7.1 Structure and Content of the Questionnaire

The state of the art for consumer testing deals only with functions up to SAE level 2. The aim of the questionnaire is to identify the requirements of users for testing functions of SAE levels 3, 4 and 5.

The stakeholders of interest for this questionnaire are:

- OEMs
- Testing facilities
- Consumer associations

The relevant topics considered in the questionnaire are here summarized:

- Defining **safety benefit** as: “how many lives could be saved and accidents avoided by the AD function” and **safety assurance** as: “the function is able to perform as expected, without adding risk to the driver or other road users”. Which is the objective of consumer testing assessment: safety benefit or safety assurance? How to prioritize then the most critical scenarios to be considered?
- Beyond functions capability, which other aspects of AD should be tested?

Euro NCAP AD working group defined 3 types of functions and 4 domains:

FUNCTIONS TYPE	Description
Assisted	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Driver retains full responsibility and shares control with the Vehicle 2. Vehicle and driver share Object and Event Detection and Response (OEDR) 3. Driver may not perform secondary tasks over and above those permitted during normal driving
Automated	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Vehicle has full responsibility for control in Operational Design Domain (ODD) defined by the OEM 2. Vehicle performs OEDR 3. Driver may perform certain other non-driving tasks 4. Driver needs to be available for safe transition of control
Autonomous	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Vehicle has full responsibility for control in Operational Design Domain (ODD) defined by the OEM 2. Vehicle performs OEDR 3. Driver is effectively a passenger 4. Driver has no ability to control (apart from switching to another mode)

FIGURE 8 EURO NCAP DEFINITIONS FOR AD FUNCTIONS

DOMAIN	Description
Parking	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Low speeds < 10 km/h 2. Parking manoeuvres, Valet Parking 3. Only Automated and Autonomous
City	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. City speeds < 60 km/h 2. City roads with crossings, roundabouts and traffic lights 3. Assisted, Automated and Autonomous
Inter-Urban	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Inter-Urban speeds <90km/h 2. Inter-Urban roads with crossings, roundabouts and traffic lights 3. Only on geofenced and qualified roads 4. Assisted, Automated and Autonomous
Highway	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Highway speeds <130km/h 2. Highways with separated and fully marked lanes (dynamic indicators) 3. Only on geofenced and qualified roads 4. Assisted, Automated and Autonomous

FIGURE 9 EURO NCAP DEFINITIONS FOR DOMAINS

About Euro NCAP AD assessment: should the star rating be used? An additional grading? How to combine the different levels and the different domains that could co-exist in the same car?

- Which is the correct approach to correctly communicate the capability and limitations of the functions to the final customers? Is SAE level a good definition? Testing the functions outside the ODD could help to understand the vehicle limits?
- Should consumer testing include different testing methodologies such as simulations, x-in-the-loop, proving ground, field operational tests? How should the scenarios then be allocated to the various testing methodologies?

7.2 Results of the Survey and Interviews

Since most of the accidents are caused by human errors, the fact that AD is intrinsically safer than manual driving is commonly accepted:

- *Defining **safety benefit** as: “how many lives could be saved and accidents avoided by the AD function” and **safety assurance** as: “the function is able to perform as expected, without adding risk to the driver or other road users”. Which is the objective of consumer testing assessment: safety benefit or safety assurance? How to prioritize then the most critical scenarios to be considered?*

OEMs agree on the fact that an essential difference between type approval and consumer testing is that the first guarantees the safety assurance while the latter focuses only on the safety benefit. They expect this difference to always exist. Regarding the prioritization of the scenarios to be tested they believe it should continue to be based on accidentology: only the most severe and critical in terms of lives cost should be assessed.

Testing facilities and consumer associations agree on the fact that type approval is about minimum requirement definition but instead they believe that consumer testing will also need to evaluate the safety assurance for AD, especially regarding the misuse possibility for the driver. About scenario prioritization they think it is not possible to use the safety benefit concept since no data on accidents dealing with L3+ functions are available at the moment.

- *Beyond functions capability, which other aspects of AD should be assessed?*
 - ODD identification and function deactivation
 - OEMs believe that this topic is part of type approval process. Consumer tests should only check if the information provided to the customers is correct.

- Testing facilities and consumer association believes it will be needed to verify if the function actually deactivates outside the ODD
 - Driver monitoring and secondary tasks
 - OEMs believe that the secondary tasks allowed will depend on the AD level and that this topic is part of national legislation. Consumer tests should only check if the information provided to the customers is correct.
 - Testing facilities and consumer association believes it will be needed to avoid misuse. Driver monitoring should always guarantee the sufficient time for the driver to take over after a transition request for L3 functions.
 - Failure modes and safety backup
 - OEMs believe that this topic is part of type approval process.
 - Testing facilities and consumer association believes it will be needed to assess also this aspect.
- *About Euro NCAP AD assessment: should the star rating be used? An additional grading? How to combine the different levels and the different domains that could co-exist in the same car?*

All the interviewees agreed to have a separate score for AD and a completely new approach, even if this makes the evaluation for the final customer more complicated.

	Parking	City	Interurban	Highway
Assisted				
Automated				
Autonomous				

Everybody believes that it will not be possible to obtain a single score value for each car since functions of different levels for the different domain could co-exist on the same vehicle.

For each cell of the matrix a different test assessment procedure is expected.

- *Which is the correct approach to correctly communicate the capability and limitations of the functions to the final customers? Is SAE level a good definition? Could testing the functions outside the ODD help the understanding?*

For all the interviewees the SAE level definitions are good to be used when dealing with technicians while for the final customer they are too complicated. The 3 definitions of Euro NCAP are simpler, even if the difference between autonomous and automated is not clear for most of the interviewees.

Communication of the limitation of the functions:

- For OEMs it is not useful to test the function outside the ODD. Only the marketing material and user manual should be used to make clear statements about the system expected use and limitations.

- Testing facilities and consumer association instead believes that, if type approval will not mandatorily require the function deactivation outside the ODD, the testing of the function outside the ODD will be useful. They believe that the customers do not realize the consequence of over-trusting the system. To show the accidents caused by a not attentive driver can reduce driver misuse of level 2 functions.
- *Should consumer testing include different testing methodologies such as simulations, x-in-the-loop, proving ground, field operational tests? How should then the scenarios to the various testing methodologies be allocated?*

The interviewees agree that a proper assessment should consider all the methodologies because for Level 3+ the list of scenarios is broad. After a common scenario database is defined it will be needed to combine simulation and physical testing because the evaluation envelope will become very large, with high number of parameters that could be modified. This implies a very high cost and time consumption if all the scenarios should be tested on proving ground.

Only some of the scenarios, the critical ones, will be tested on proving ground. Self-assessment (OEMs performing assessment and providing results) will become more and more important because more information about the performance of the system will be asked to be provided from OEMs. The experimental test will be strictly based on what they declare. Physical tests will later verify some specific scenarios to obtain the same results.

OEMs think that field operational tests could be used too, but their final target must be clearly stated.

8 Testing goal for KETs

The current stage in the project is to define and develop test, validation and certification methodologies and procedures for CAD building upon existing initiatives. HEADSTART will develop testing, validation and certification methodologies and procedures for CAD by: closing existing gaps and developing methodologies, procedures and tools beyond state-of-the-art. For the gaps identified, HEADSTART will develop methodologies, procedures and tools for the testing and validation of highly automated functions and its KET's according to stakeholder requirements, current state-of-the-art and in coordination with ongoing initiatives.

8.1 Structure and Content of the Questionnaire

In order to enable HEADSTART to "develop testing, validation and certification methodologies and procedures for CAD by: closing existing gaps and developing methodologies, procedures and tools beyond state-of-the-art."

The specific purpose of this questionnaire is to collect the Stakeholders (ex : OEM, Tier 1, Testing facility, Regulatory) use case, with the specific associated testing needs with regards to communication, cyber-security, positioning. Requirements will be extracted from the elaborated testing needs and used to create a catalogue of the (new) testable aspects of KET's (i.e. communication, cyber-security, positioning), that is not competently satisfied (or that has some aspects that need developing) under the current testing methodologies (paradigm).

8.2 Results of the Survey and Interviews

There were 16 responders to the questionnaire in total at the time of the writing. In the post of "Others" there were one university, three engineering partners and one transport provider.

FIGURE 10 RESULT OF THE STAKEHOLDER CATEGORIES.

The responders categorized their use case to mostly belong one of three general groups.

FIGURE 11 WHICH ETRAC GENERAL CATEGORY DOES THE USE CASE MOSTLY BELONG TO.

FIGURE 12 WHAT KIND OF STAKE-HOLD WOULD YOU CONSIDER IS OF PRIMARY CONCERN FOR YOUR USER NEED?

The distribution of responders had a good spread over the stakeholder categories, and thus providing a good coverage to the user testing needs of KETs. From the answers of use case categories one can deduce that the three main categories have a good fit. The primary concern in user testing needs is in falling order, testing and validation, certification and assessment.

The use cases that have testing goals for KET's can at the top level be seen to adhere to one of three categories.

- Automated Freight Vehicles
- Automated Passenger Cars
- Urban Mobility Vehicles

In order to have a common understanding of the terms used in discussing the levels of automated systems of interest here, the taxonomy of SAE J3016 will be used. The taxonomy provides detailed definitions for six levels of driving automation, ranging from no driving automation (level 0) to full driving automation (level 5) within the 3 categories mentioned above.

There is a possibility to have a good map of how the testing needs or goals of KET's relate to automation levels if a mapping is done in each category.

The use case list for each category was collected from Connected Automated Driving Roadmap from ERTRAC¹³.

FIGURE 13 ERTRAC USE CASE LIST FOR AUTOMATED FREIGHT VEHICLE APPLICATIONS

To make it clear what the diagram is telling us Highly automated freight vehicles in Hub-to-Hub operation (Level 4) Automated Truck Platooning (Level 2) is of main concern.

¹³ <https://www.ertrac.org/uploads/documentsearch/id57/ERTRAC-CAD-Roadmap-2019.pdf>

FIGURE 14 ERTRAC USE CASE LIST AUTOMATED PASSENGER CAR APPLICATION

To make it clear what the diagram is telling us: Urban and Suburban Pilot (Level 4), Autonomous private vehicles on public roads (Level 5), Traffic Jam Chauffeur (Level 3), Autonomous private vehicles on public roads (Level 5), Highway Autopilot (Level 4) and Urban and Suburban Pilot (Level 4) is of main concern.

FIGURE 15 ERTRAC USE CASE LIST URBAN MOBILITY VEHICLE APPLICATIONS

To make it clear what the diagram is telling us: Highly automated freight vehicles in Fully Automated Urban Vehicles (Level 5), Automated PRT/Shuttles on dedicated roads (Level 4) and Automated Bus Chauffeur (Level 3) is of main concern.

9 Outcome of the workshop and use case prioritisation

A workshop was organised on June 12th at the ESV conference in Eindhoven (NL) to introduce the objectives of the HEADSTART project to more than 40 industry experts and collect their opinion on the topics of Use case and scenario selection as well as Consumer testing. A prioritisation of use cases was presented based on the interviews' first results. The views of industry experts on this prioritisation were then collected during an open discussion session.

The following figures and tables were presented to the experts, they show the priority use cases, their associated AD functions, their description, benefits, associated risks and challenges.

FIGURE 16 OVERVIEW OF THE PRIORITY USE CASES – HEADSTART WORKSHOP AT ESV – 12TH OF JUNE

TABLE 3: SUMMARY OF USE-CASES : HIGHWAY PILOT & TRAFFIC JAM CHAUFFEUR

	Highway pilot	Traffic jam chauffeur
CAD function & autonomy level (SAE)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Highway Chauffeur (SAE level 3) Highway Autopilot (SAE level 4) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Traffic Jam Assist (SAE level 2) Traffic Jam Chauffeur (SAE level 3)
Description	Passenger cars, at high speed, on highway	Passenger cars, up to 60 km/h, on highway/motorway
Priority	Priority for 88% of the stakeholders interviewed (OEMs, Public authorities, Research institutes, consumer organisations)	Priority for 38% of the stakeholders interviewed (OEMs, Research institutes)
Benefits	Comfort , Safety, Fuel Saving, better traffic	Safety , Comfort, Fuel saving
Main risks and challenges	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Over trusting the system, Using the function outside the ODD, Adaptability to other countries, System not interpreting the situation correctly, Ability to manage different weather conditions, 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Over trusting the system, Using the function outside the ODD, Adaptability to other countries, Manage different weather conditions, Interactions with the driver

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Minimum Risk Maneuver & HMI (SAE level 3) • Risky for the OEMs (SAE level 3) 	
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TABLE 4: SUMMARY OF USE-CASES : VALET PARKING & URBAN PILOT

	Valet parking	Urban pilot
CAD function & autonomy level (SAE)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Parking Assist (SAE level 2) • Parking Garage Pilot (SAE level 4) • Automated Valet Parking (SAE level 4) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Urban and Suburban Pilot (SAE level 4)
Description	Passenger cars, in a parking garage or on the street, driver inside or outside the vehicle.	Passenger cars, urban roads, at speed limit
Priority	Priority for 29% of the stakeholders interviewed (OEMs, Research institutes)	Priority for 12% of the stakeholders interviewed (Research institutes)
Benefits	Convenient, Saving time , More parking space	Safety, Convenient
Main risks and challenges	The infrastructure needs to be adapted for the parking garage pilot.	Interactions with pedestrians and bicycles, sensor limitation Too complicated to implement, It is not yet feasible to manage all the scenarios in an urban environment.

TABLE 5: SUMMARY OF USE-CASES : AUTOMATED SHUTTLE FOR URBAN & TRUCK PLATOONING

	Automated shuttle for urban	Truck platooning
CAD function & autonomy level (SAE)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Automated Shuttles on dedicated roads (SAE level 4) • Automated Shuttles in mixed traffic (SAE level 4) • Robotaxis: Fully Automated Urban Vehicles (SAE level 5) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Automated Truck Platooning (SAE level 2) • Highway Pilot platooning (SAE level 4)
Description	Urban Mobility Vehicles, low speed	Freight vehicles, up to 80 Km/h, on highway
Priority	Priority for 29% of the stakeholders interviewed (OEMs, public authority)	Priority for 29% of the stakeholders interviewed (Research institutes)
Benefits	Safety, Good for customer who cannot drive, no driver cost, Reduced pollution.	Improved efficiency/operability for freight companies , driver comfort, saving manpower, Save fuel, less wind resistance.

Main risks and challenges	Criminal activity (Cyber-attack), Interactions with pedestrians, The system has to understand complex situations. Robotaxi: Too complicated to implement, It is not yet feasible to manage all the scenarios in an urban environment.	Loss of communication or positioning , criminal activities (cyber-attack, false signal). Not being able to read the signs. Safety risk due to the short distance between trucks and high speed
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Following the presentation, the experts participated in an open discussion session where they shared their opinion on the results of the interviews and the priority use cases presented.

The main comments made were:

Among the level 3 automated functions, Highway will be out first on the market. But KETs are not needed. **Traffic jam** is seen as a sub-function of highway pilot.

Valet parking is already available. But this function is used for a short time and needs specific safety requirements. It needs localization and V2X and specific infrastructures. This use-case is not relevant for testing in consumer testing.

For Truck platooning, V2X is needed, it depends on the traffic laws of the different countries.

Autonomous shuttles need geofenced areas, positioning and HD mapping

Highway pilot and **urban driving** will have the bigger safety impact. **Urban driving** will be implemented with automated shuttles first.

It is possible that SAE level 4 will come before SAE level 3. SAE level 3 vehicle might not arrive at all for highway functions.

10 Analysis of user groups needs

10.1 Use cases and Scenarios

In this section, we are going to discuss the results of the interviews presented in Chapter 3 on the topic of Use cases and scenarios and present the main user needs expressed.

The various stakeholders interviewed during this task brought up different use cases as a priority, the main use cases mentioned are:

Type of vehicle	Priority use cases	% of stakeholders interviewed
For passenger cars:	Highway pilot	88%
	Traffic jam chauffeur	38%
	Valet parking	29%
For freight vehicles:	Truck platooning	29%
For urban mobility vehicles:	Low speed automated shuttle for urban	29%

Some other use cases were mentioned during the interviews but are not considered as a priority due to their difficulty to implement. These secondary use cases are:

- Urban pilot (SAE level 4)
- Robot taxi (SAE level 5)

10.1.1 Highway Pilot

The highway pilot use case can be described as the automated driving of SAE level 3 or 4 for passenger cars at high speed on highway or motorway similar roads, from entrance to exit, on all lanes, including overtaking. The driver must deliberately activate the system but does not have to monitor the system constantly. The driver can at all times override or switch off the system. In case of a takeover request to the driver from the system, the driver has enough time reserve to orientate him/herself and take over the driving task. In case the driver does not take over, the system will go to a reduced risk condition, i.e. bring the vehicle to a safe stop. If possible depending on the traffic situation and system capabilities, the reduced risk conditions will include the necessary lane changes to stop at the hard shoulder e.g. emergency lane or side of the road [ERTRAC roadmap 2019¹⁴].

This use case includes the CAD functions **Highway Chauffeur (SAE level 3)** and **Highway Autopilot (SAE level 4)**

Overall, 88% of the stakeholders interviewed described the highway pilot use case as a priority use case for the industry. These stakeholders belong to the categories of OEMs, public authorities and research institutes (including proving ground).

The main benefits of this use case for the consumers is the added comfort while driving as well as the possibility to focus on something else than the driving task. For the OEMs, this use case is easier to implement than other use cases such as urban driving because the scenarios encountered are easier to handle even at high speed.

It is important to note that some of the stakeholders do not believe that SAE level 3 will be out on the market because of the challenges of Minimum Risk Manoeuvre (MRM) during emergency take over and the associated Human Machine Interface. If the legal responsibility is transferred to the OEM, then the SAE level 3 use cases are too risky to release.

¹⁴ <https://www.ertrac.org/uploads/documentsearch/id57/ERTRAC-CAD-Roadmap-2019.pdf>

10.1.2 Traffic jam chauffeur

This use case can be described as conditional automated driving in traffic jam up to 60 km/h on highway and motorway similar roads. The system can be activated in case of a traffic jam scenario. It detects slow driving vehicle in front and then handles the vehicle's both longitudinal and lateral. Later version of this functionality might include lane change functionality. The driver must deliberately activate the system but does not have to monitor the system constantly. The driver can at all times override or switch off the system. In case of a takeover request to the driver from the system, the driver has sufficient time reserve to orientate himself and take over the driving task. In case the driver does not take over, the system will go to a reduced risk condition, i.e. bring the vehicle to a safe stop [ERTRAC roadmap 2019]. This use case can include functions of SAE level 3 and 4.

Overall, 38% of the stakeholders interviewed described traffic jam chauffeur as a priority use case for the industry. These stakeholders belong to the categories of OEMs and research institutes (including proving ground). This use case was described as a sub-function of highway pilot by the experts who participated in the workshop. Most stakeholders interviewed said that traffic jam chauffeur would be available on the market before highway pilot as the speed targeted by this use case is lower and the scenarios easier to handle.

The main benefit of this use case is safety because it will help maintain a safe distance between vehicles reducing the risk of rear end collision.

10.1.3 Valet parking

The valet parking use case is regrouping two distinct CAD functions depending on the type of parking:

Parking Garage Pilot (SAE level 4)

Highly Automated parking including manoeuvring to and from parking place (driverless valet parking). In parking garage, the driver does not have to monitor the system constantly and may leave once the system is active. Via smartphone or key, parking manoeuvre and return of the vehicle is initiated [ERTRAC roadmap 2019].

Automated Valet Parking (SAE level 4)

Highly Automated parking including manoeuvring in a limited area with limited speed to and from most parking spaces. The driver can leave the vehicle and initiates the manoeuvring to the parking space and the parking itself by e.g. smartphone or key. He does not have to monitor the system constantly and may initiate the parking-out manoeuvre the same way when coming back [ERTRAC roadmap 2019].

29% of the stakeholders interviewed considered Valet parking a priority use case for the industry. These stakeholders belong to the categories of OEMs, and research institutes.

Partial automated parking function already exists on the market and the technology could be extended to higher level of automation. The main benefit of the valet parking use case is that it is convenient and saving time for the consumer.

10.1.4 Automated shuttle for urban

This use case regroups several Automated PRT/Shuttles functions described in the ERTRAC Connected Automated Driving roadmap. These low-speed automated shuttles can be limited to a dedicated area / dedicated road or lane or be adapted to drive in mixed traffic. There will be no passenger intervention in driving task, in case of emergency, the vehicle is able to reach a safe stop. In some cases, an operator can control the vehicle remotely. The main challenge linked to this use case is the interaction with pedestrians, cyclist and other vulnerable road users.

This use case is a priority for 29% of the stakeholders interviewed. These stakeholders belong to the categories of OEMs and Public authorities.

The main benefit of automated shuttle are safety and convenience for the people who cannot drive or want to travel the “last mile”.

10.1.5 Truck platooning

The truck platooning use case includes the Highway Pilot platooning function for freight vehicles (SAE level 4). It can be defined as: Automated Driving on motorways or highways from entrance to exit, on all lanes, including overtaking and lane change. The driver must deliberately activate the system, but does not have to monitor the system constantly. The driver can at all-time override or switch off the system. There is no request from the system to the driver to take over when the system is in normal operation area (i.e. on the motorway) [ERTRAC roadmap 2019].

29% of the stakeholders interviewed have described this use case as a priority for the industry. These stakeholders are mostly research institutes involved in truck platooning projects.

Truck platooning will greatly benefit the freights companies with an improved efficiency and operability. The main concern with this use case is the risk of loss of communication and positioning.

10.2 Safety assessment and safety case

In this section, the results of the interviews presented in Chapter 3 on the topic of safety assessment and safety case will be discussed and the main user needs expressed presented.

10.2.1 Risks introduced by CAD

Connected and automated driving is a new technology and its introduction to the market brings new challenges to road safety. During the interviews on Safety assessment and safety case, the stakeholders were asked about the new risks introduced by CAD, the main risks identified are:

The risk of misusing the system: For lower level of autonomy (mainly SAE level 1/2/3), if the driver is not well aware of the Operational Design Domain (ODD) for the automated function used, there is a risk of activating the function outside of its ODD (e.g. activating a highway chauffeur function on a suburban road). This will highly increase the risk of accident.

Encountering an unknown scenario: as there is an infinite number of scenarios that the system can encounter, some safety relevant scenarios are too rare and complex and cannot be mastered by the system. This number of complex scenarios increases in an urban environment with pedestrians and other vulnerable road users. In some cases, the sensors are limiting the perception of the vehicle and as a result, the system is not as efficient in handling complex situations as a human driver.

Software update and bugs: The system updates can represent a risk if they affect the behaviour of the car (e.g. update to a higher level of autonomy). These updates have to be tested and approved one by one to ensure that they are safe. Another risk for the system are bugs. Bugs represent a threat to the safety of the driver (e.g. the function activates by itself or stops functioning without warning the driver).

Criminal activities / cyber-attack: implementing cyber-security on CAD is crucial for protecting the driver and the public.

Loss of positioning / Connectivity: some use cases are heavily relying on these key enabling technologies (e.g. truck platooning), so it is vital that the system is able to function without them in case of emergency, at least temporarily to reach a safe state (e.g. stop on the emergency lane).

In any case, the risks have to be assessed. In order to be acceptable, a balance needs to be found between possible new risk created against the benefits brought by these new technologies.

10.2.2 Methodology and procedures for CAD safety.

When asked about the best approach to take to ensure the safety of Connected and Automated Vehicles, most of the stakeholders agreed that the scenario-based approach is a good solution. It is essential to use a combination of different test instances (simulation, test track and open road) to validate the vehicle for different scenarios found for a specific use case.

In terms of procedure and tools, most stakeholders agree that the Safety Of The Intended Functionality (SOTIF)¹⁵ is complementary to the traditional functional safety approach (ISO 26262) and is a good procedure to follow to ensure the safety of CAD functions.

10.2.3 Legislation for CAD safety

When asked about the legislation existing for CAD safety at national or international level, most stakeholders agree that the legislation for higher level of autonomy (SAE level 3 and more) is almost inexistent and the question of the legal responsibility needs to be clarified.

10.3 Testing

In this section the results of chapter 3 are discussed and user group needs are derived from the evaluation of the interviews. It can be seen that most of the testing is taking place on SAE levels 2 and 3. Nevertheless, most of the interviewed stakeholders stated that their testing is progressing through SAE level 3+ in the near future. Therefore, new testing capabilities and methodologies are necessary. Especially, performance and validation tests are in the focus of testing organisations. There were no fixed methodologies stated except from protocols like EuroNCAP. Thus a need for a common methodology and protocol like instruction catalogue for testing is needed.

10.4 Certification/ Type approval (tools, procedures)

Compared to conventional vehicles, the complexity of the systems, safety areas and possible scenarios of automated vehicles will increase and it will be difficult to fully assess them with a limited track and predefined performance tests. Therefore, a new certification solution has to be developed, and has to take into account all the safety aspects of the vehicle, including the applied processes and design methods for the system development.

It is not intended to replace the classical certification method, because physical tests are still needed in order to evaluate some physical performance requirements such as braking performance with and without failures, engine emissions and others. For this reason, a new certification concept known as “Multi-Pillar Certification Approach” has been developed and discussed during the last meetings in UNECE WP.29 and its subsidiary working group GRVA.

The concept currently includes three main pillars, but could be augmented by additional pillars as needed for other vehicle aspects evaluation. The three pillars are: Audit and Assessment, Physical Certification Tests, and Real World Test Drive. The idea is that the scope of work will be reduced with every step, as first step of audit and assessment will include simulation results and the whole assessment of the safety concept, but the final certification will depend on the assessment of all the pillars.

The main purpose of the pillars is:

- **Audit and Assessment:** Evaluation and assessment of the design processes, test methods for the development of Hardware and Software. Also special requirements for fault strategy and verification with respect to the safety aspects of Complex Electronic Systems are assessed, in order to see that the performance requirements under non-fault and fault conditions will not lead to critical risks. Also virtual

¹⁵ From the standard: ISO/PAS 21448 : 2019

simulation is included in this pillar; it is possible to check the vehicle behaviour with different input parameters, scenarios and focusing in special cases that could be difficult to reproduce with real tests.

- **Physical Certification Tests:** with physical tests allows to evaluate performance requirements such as braking or steering effort as it is currently done in the “classical certification”.
With the results obtained during the first pillar assessment and the simulation, specific critical tests cases for the vehicle can be performed physically, so that real behaviour can be compared with results obtained before. In addition, there is no risk of injuries in scenarios where vulnerable road users, buildings or other drivers are involved.
- **Real World Test Drive:** finally, real test drive is needed to assess that the vehicle handles non simulated traffic scenarios. The operational design domain is also under study during this phase, as well as human machine interface requirements.

WP.29 and each of its relevant subsidiary Working Parties on Automated/Autonomous vehicles, agreed on key aspects to be considered to be taken into account to ensure the safety.¹⁶

System Safety

The manufacturer shall follow a robust design and validation process with the goal of designing driving systems free of risks and ensuring compliance with traffic regulations. Hazard analysis and safety risk assessment should be taken into account for the overall vehicle in this topic.

As it is very difficult to simulate all the variables of the real traffic world in simulations, it could be also necessary to tests the ego vehicle in the real traffic scenario.

Failsafe Response

It is important to ensure that automated driving systems are designed with specific processes for handover of the driving task to the driver with minimal risk condition when the vehicle is not able to handle a situation in a safe mode. Virtual simulation could be a good tool because some cases are difficult to be reproduced as well as their failures during real world tests.

Human-Machine Interface

If needed, the vehicle should incorporate driver engagement monitoring where driver could be involved in the driving task to assess that the driver is controlling the environment and would be ready to take over the driving task. Documentation for all HMI should be needed, and if possible, should be tested accordingly.

On the other hand, open road tests could also be useful to review the reaction of other road users, and to complement the track testing.

Object Event Detection and Response (OEDR)

The vehicle shall be able to detect and avoid or respond to objects or events reasonably expected in its operational domain. Virtual simulation will be needed for this topic, because pedestrian dummies and car balloon behaviour are not realistic in most of the real tests. With virtual simulation it is possible to reproduce alternative scenarios, and also the System in the Loop simulation can be used, which allows complex real time tests with high degree of repeatability.

¹⁶ Full document is available on:

https://www.unece.org/fileadmin/DAM/trans/doc/2019/wp29grva/SE_vs_MPA_v2.2.xlsx

Operational Domain (OD)

The operational domain of each autonomous system shall be defined and documented as well as all the procedures and process carried out for this assessment, including testing and validation of the system on the ODD.

In this case, real world test and simulation are the best options for the assessment, as some systems are using GPS signal in order to activate or deactivate some of the functions, thus, this would cover more possible scenarios.

Validation for System Safety

Cyber-Security

Introduces a Cyber Security Management System, where the manufacturer shall protect against cyber-attacks their systems in accordance with existing standards and best practices.

A draft recommendation on Cyber Security has been launched by a specialized informal group of GRVA¹⁷. The paper defines principles to address key cyber-attacks and vulnerabilities in order to assure vehicle safety. In addition, it also defines guidance and measures for how to meet all the described principles.

Assessments and documentations of the evidences of compliance shall be demonstrated in order to be certified.

Software Updates

System updates will provide for after-market modifications on many systems. These updates can repair or modify some systems that could be critical for the safety behaviour of the vehicle. These updates should only be done with the previous validation of the user, but in cases of system repairing, there shall also be means to verify and identify if the target vehicles are using the new software version. In any case, it is important to ensure that all the updates are carried out in a safe mode without putting the vehicle at risk.

A dedicated task force belonging to GRVA developed a draft paper with requirements and recommendations of how to ensure the safety with software updates, whether it is physically or over-the-air¹⁸.

The recommendation describes requirements for adaptation of vehicle software updates for certification to ensure their safe execution and legal compliance with the regulation under UN program of work.

Data Storage System for Automated Driving Vehicles (DSSAD)

DSSAD are systems that collect and store a determinate range of vehicle data. This system is intended for vehicle crash studies including the status of the automated driving system and status of the driver.

Remote Operation

It is understood for unmanned urban transport such as interurban bus shuttle. In this case it would be mandatory to assess functional safety during the development phase, but it will also be mandatory to tests on proving ground and with real-world test drive, to ensure that the vehicle receives good connectivity and its behaviour is as expected.

¹⁷ Draft recommendation on Cyber Security available on:

<https://www.unece.org/fileadmin/DAM/trans/doc/2018/wp29grva/GRVA-01-17.pdf>

¹⁸ Draft recommendations for the software updates available on:

<https://www.unece.org/fileadmin/DAM/trans/doc/2018/wp29grva/GRVA-01-18.pdf>

Safety of In-Use Vehicles

Maintenance and inspection of automated vehicles are key aspects to ensure the safety and security during the life cycle. New requirements on Periodical Technical Inspection will arise in the near future, and WP.29 dedicated subgroup is already working on it.

Consumer Education and Training

Finally, it is possible that consumer education and training programmes on automated systems will be part of type approval. The requirements could be checked by an initial audit and document verification.

10.5 Consumer testing

Based on the answers received during the questionnaires we can conclude that there is no clear alignment between testing facilities/consumer associations and OEMs regarding the topic that are expected to be tested during the AD assessments.

The main concern of consumer associations is to correctly communicate the capability and limitations of the functions to the final customer in order to avoid the possibility of misuse. This is strictly related to the actual capability of the functions (that is SAE level 2) since the driver must always be in the loop but currently this is not guaranteed by the function itself. Some vehicles lead the driver to over-trust the capability of the functions.

About SAE level 3+ functions, this could not be needed depending strictly on the minimum requirements settled by type approval. It is a common expectation that the type approval minimum requirements will already be strict for the topic of function activation: SAE level 3+ functions are expected to be activated only in geo-fenced areas.

OEMs instead would like to keep the current approach of consumer assessment based on the safety benefit concept. This approach at the moment seems difficult to be applied due to the lack of evidences about accidents involving level 3+ functions and thus due to the impossibility to define the most critical scenarios based on real-world data.

Dedicated Euro NCAP WG on Virtual assessment is expected to start in coming months, both for active and passive safety. They will work to find a link between simulations and track tests. It will be needed to define rules for simulation models refinement and to compile a list of evidences to be provided in order to prove with an adequate level of confidence that the simulation results are reliable. HEADSTART methodology could help to fill the gap of model validation defining criteria for the evaluation and the comparison between results obtained in physical tests and in simulation.

To understand which scenario should be assessed in physical testing and which in simulation is a hot topic in Euro NCAP working group. No answer is now available so the results of HEADSTART dealing with scenario allocation will be useful for this kind of decisions.

The KETs are not topic of discussion in the AD working group at the moment but a scenario dealing with connectivity is expected to be included from 2024.

Finally, about the testing matrix, everybody agrees that it will be necessary to define different scenarios for each domain (parking, urban, interurban, highway) and each function type (assisted/automated/autonomous). This is only partially in counter-tendency with the objective of HEADSTART to build a harmonized methodology for CAD validation. The scenario database can be successfully differentiated depending on the domain but for L3+ cars the objective is to have a single validation methodology. For consumer testing assessment the presence of a human driver that must be able to take control when requested is fundamental to define additional requirements for automated vehicle with respect to autonomous vehicles.

10.6 Testing goal for KETs

The use cases that have testing goals for KET's can at the top level be seen to adhere to one of three categories.

- Automated Freight Vehicles
- Automated Passenger Cars
- Urban Mobility Vehicles

In order to have a common understanding of the terms used in discussing the levels of automated systems of interest here, the taxonomy of SAE J3016 will be used. The taxonomy provides detailed definitions for six levels of driving automation, ranging from no driving automation (level 0) to full driving automation (level 5) within the 3 categories mentioned above. There is a possibility to have a good map of how the testing needs or goals of KET's relate to automation levels if a mapping is done in each category. The use case list for each category was collected from Connected Automated Driving Roadmap from ERTRAC¹⁹.

Testing for Key Enabling Technologies (KET) of interest here are positioning, communication and cybersecurity. The KET's can be mapped to automation levels and category of type of application and the goals of the testing will have to be to ensure testability for these application (listed in Table 6: List of applications to be mapped with requirements for KETs below) in their environment. The refinement of this mapping to requirements for testing goals of KET's will be done in deliverable D1.3 within the project.

The initial testing goals of the KETs will be to ensure testability for, at least, these applications in their environment, since this is an initial analysis it is certain that this scope will expand or change over time.

TABLE 6: LIST OF APPLICATIONS TO BE MAPPED WITH REQUIREMENTS FOR KETs

List of applications to be mapped with requirements for KETs
Highly automated freight vehicles in Hub-to-Hub operation (Level 4)
Automated Truck Platooning (Level 2)
Urban and Suburban Pilot (Level 4)
Autonomous private vehicles on public roads (Level 5)
Traffic Jam Chauffeur (Level 3)
Autonomous private vehicles on public roads (Level 5)
Highway Autopilot (Level 4)
Urban and Suburban Pilot (Level 4)
Highly automated freight vehicles in Fully Automated Urban Vehicles (Level 5)
Automated PRT/Shuttles on dedicated roads (Level 4)
Automated Bus Chauffeur (Level 3)

¹⁹ <https://www.ertrac.org/uploads/documentsearch/id57/ERTRAC-CAD-Roadmap-2019.pdf>

11 Conclusion and implications

The work carried out during the task 1.2 of HEADSTART allowed us to identify the needs on methodologies, procedures, tools and standards for relevant user groups and stakeholders from the HEADSTART consortium as well as across the value chain.

There was a strong participation of stakeholders from across the value chain with 44 answers to our interviews and an ongoing online survey. There is also a good repartition of the interviewees. The research institutes, engineering companies and proving ground facilities were the most represented in our interviews. OEMs and automotive suppliers were also well represented thanks to their involvement in the consortium or as a supporter of the project. We also collected the views of several public authorities and policy makers. We note that consumer organisations were not well represented in these interviews and will be solicited again for the ongoing online survey.

Overall, the level of precision of the answers for each interview is very satisfying and shows a great interest in the project. These needs expressed were presented to a group of experts during a workshop on 12 June 2019 in Eindhoven (NL) to collect their views on the topics and confirm a first prioritisation of use cases.

We can observe that the expectations of the OEMs are homogeneous but that they are waiting for the evolution of the legislation as well as consumerism for the SAE level 3+ functions. The problematic of having a common methodology, a catalogue of scenarios and mature technologies is still everyone's main concern to justify safety of CAD functions. The HEADSTART project has built its response according to this problematic.

Following the prioritisation of use cases based on stakeholder's needs, up to four use cases will be selected according to the following criteria:

- **The scenarios are available**
- **The technology is mature and representative enough**
- **Cover all the KETs**
- **Feasibility within the project scope and timeline**

These requirements for selecting the use-cases will be detailed in the task 1.4 of HEADSTART. Overall, the needs identified during the interviews as well as the use cases prioritised will be exploited in the following steps of the project:

- Task 1.3 will use the result of the interviews and surveys to identify the requirements for the Key Enabling Technologies (KETs)
- Task 1.4 will use the priority use cases identified in the interviews and confirmed by the expert group to establish the functional requirements for each use case and select up to four use cases for the HEADSTART project.
- Task 2.3 will map its criteria for optimal scenarios with the user group needs defined in task 1.2.

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Annex 1: Questionnaire on Type Approval

1) The priorities set out by the WP.29 (World Forum for the Harmonization of Vehicle Regulations) of the UNECE are as follows:

- Framework Document on AD vehicles
- Functional Requirements: ACSF, CEL, ALKS and PTI
- New Assessment/ Test Method (VMAD)
- Data Storage System for Automated Driving (DSSAD)
- Cyber Security (CS)
- Over the Air Updates (OTA)
- Modular Vehicle Combinations (MVC)
- Automatic Emergency Braking Systems (AEBS)
- Event Data Recorder (EDR)

Do you agree with the list? What more could be done in terms of standardization to make sure that new technologies penetrate the market while at the same time keeping their promise on safety?

2) Vehicle safety standards are defined in Geneva, at world level. During the last year, the structure of the Working Group on Autonomous Vehicles has changed several times to address the most critical aspects in the short term. In the last session, the Chair of the GRVA working group proposed to continue working under the following structure:

Figure 1 Informal Working Groups of GRVA. Source: GRVA-02-47 UNECE

Is this the right format? What changes would you propose and why?

3) During the last months several draft regulations have been issued:

- Draft proposal to introduce UN Regulation on Cyber Security
<https://www.unece.org/fileadmin/DAM/trans/doc/2019/wp29grva/ECE-TRANS-WP29-GRVA-2019-02e.pdf>

- Draft proposal to introduce UN Regulation on Software Updates
<https://www.unece.org/fileadmin/DAM/trans/doc/2019/wp29grva/ECE-TRANS-WP29-GRVA-2019-03e.pdf>
- Draft proposal to amend existing UN Regulations to introduce Software Identification numbers (RWXSWIN)
<https://www.unece.org/fileadmin/DAM/trans/doc/2019/wp29grva/ECE-TRANS-WP29-GRVA-2019-03e.pdf>
- Proposal for a new draft UN Regulation on AEBs for M1 and N1
<https://www.unece.org/fileadmin/DAM/trans/doc/2019/wp29grva/ECE-TRANS-WP29-GRVA-2019-05e.pdf>
- Amendments for UN Regulation No. 79 (Steering equipment) , No. 139 (Brake Assist System), No. 140 (Electronic Stability Control).
<https://www.unece.org/fileadmin/DAM/trans/doc/2019/wp29grva/ECE-TRANS-WP29-GRVA-2019-04e.pdf>
<https://www.unece.org/fileadmin/DAM/trans/doc/2019/wp29grva/ECE-TRANS-WP29-GRVA-2019-06e.pdf>
<https://www.unece.org/fileadmin/DAM/trans/doc/2019/wp29grva/ECE-TRANS-WP29-GRVA-2019-12e.pdf>

Which other “Regulatory gaps” do you identify in today’s Regulatory Framework? Which of them should be considered a priority?

- 4) Currently the UN/ECE is defining the first “use cases” for automation level 3. Moreover, ERTRAC has issued its report about the deployment expectations.

Figure 2 Automated Driving development path for passenger cars. Source: Connected Automated Driving Roadmap, ERTRAC 2019.

From the Type Approval point of view, do you agree with this forecast? When do you expect level 3 vehicles on the road?

- 5) The International Organization of Motor Vehicle Manufacturers (OICA) has proposed a new concept for Certification based on three main pillars: Audit and Assessment, Physical Certification Tests and Real World Test Drive (see image below).

Figure 3 The three pillar's approach. Source: OICA, GRVA/2019/13

What would be the main impacts of this new approach? What kind of new test procedures and technologies do we need to test automated vehicles during type approval in the future?

- 6) Today we already have a harmonization of the testing procedure for OBD emission testing. Do think we need the same for the safety systems?
- 7) Regarding Periodic Technical Inspection (PTI), what should in your view the vehicle testing world do to evolve in parallel to Type Approval procedures?
- 8) Considering that new technologies will rise new consumer behaviours (like e.g. Car Sharing). What Cities could/should do at a national level to contribute with the deployment of the highly automated vehicles?

Type Approval and Certification procedures

INTRODUCTION

HEADSTART (Harmonised European Solutions for Testing Automated Road Transport) is a new European initiative that aims to define testing and validation procedures on specific functionalities of Connected and Automated Driving (CAD). HEADSTART will define testing and validation procedures of functions including its key enabling technologies by cross-linking of all test instances such as simulation, proving ground and real-world field tests to validate safety and security performance according to the needs of key user groups (technology developers, consumer testing and type approval).

The current stage in the project is to define and develop test, validation and certification methodologies and procedures for CAD building upon existing initiatives. HEADSTART will develop testing, validation and certification methodologies and procedures for CAD by: closing existing gaps and developing methodologies, procedures and tools beyond state-of-the-art. For the gaps identified, HEADSTART will develop methodologies, procedures and tools for the testing and validation of highly automated functions and its KET's according to stakeholder requirements, current state-of-the-art and in coordination with ongoing initiatives.

PURPOSE OF QUESTIONNAIRE

In order to enable HEADSTART to "develop testing, validation and certification methodologies and procedures for CAD by: closing existing gaps and developing methodologies, procedures and tools beyond state-of-the-art." The purpose of this survey is to collect the Stakeholders needs (e.g. OEM, Automotive Suppliers, Testing facility, Regulatory Entity) on methodologies, procedures, tools and standards for demonstrations and certifications of different use-cases. Results of this survey will be used to build a prioritisation of use-cases that will be reviewed by different user groups through a workshop.

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1

Which among the priorities of WP.29 of the UNECE do you see more critical/prime?

- Framework Document on AD vehicles
- Functional Requirements: ACSF, CEL, ALKS and PTI
- New Assessment/ Test Method (VMAD)
- Data Storage System for Automated Driving (DSSAD)
- Cyber Security (CS)
- Over the Air Updates (OTA)
- Modular Vehicle Combinations (MVC)
- Automatic Emergency Braking Systems (AEBS)
- Event Data Recorder (EDR)

2

Do you agree with the current structure of the GRVA of WP 29 UNECE?

Yes

No

3

If you answered 'No' in the previous question, what would you change?

Entrez votre réponse

4

Which other "Regulatory gaps" do you identify in today's Regulatory Framework?

Entrez votre réponse

5

Could you list them in priority order? (priority 1 :..., priority 2 :....., priority 3 :.....)

Entrez votre réponse

6

Do you agree with the following forecast (Source: ERTRAC)?

- Yes
- No

7

If you answered 'No' in the previous question, could you please explain the reason?

Entrez votre réponse

8

When do you expect Level 3 completely deployed and on the road?

Veuillez entrer la date au format dd/MM/yyyy

9

Do you agree with the OICA proposal for certification based on the three pillars?

Analysis/Assessment

- Understand the system to be certified
- Assess that the applied processes and development methods for the overall system development (SW and HW) are effective, complete and consistent
- Assess system's architectural performance to address (qualitative) fault-conditions and disturbances due to deteriorating external influences, vehicle behaviour in variation of critical scenarios
- Simulations: Test parameters variations (e.g. distances, speed) of scenarios and edge-cases that are difficult to test safely on a test track

Simulation

- Assess critical scenarios that are technically difficult for the system, have a high safety potential and are representative for real traffic
- Compare with manual test cases defined from simulations and validate simulation work

Physical Certification Tests

- Assess the overall system capabilities and behavior in non-structured traffic on public roads and show that the system has not been optimized on specific test scenarios
- Assess system safety improvements like e.g. RMI and ODD
- Assess that the system achieves a performance comparable to an experienced driver

- Yes
- No

10

If you answered 'No' in the previous question, could you please explain the reason?

Entrez votre réponse

What would be the main impacts of this new approach? What kind of new test procedures and

11

Today we already have a harmonization of the testing procedure for OBD emission testing. Do think we need the same for the safety systems?

Yes

No

12

If you answered 'No' in the previous question, could you please explain the reason?

Entrez votre réponse

13

What kind of new test procedures and technologies do we need to test automated vehicles during type approval in the future?

Entrez votre réponse

14

Regarding Periodic Technical Inspection (PTI), what should in your view the vehicle testing world do to evolve in parallel to Type Approval procedures?

Entrez votre réponse

15

Considering that new technologies will rise new consumer behaviours (like e.g. Car Sharing). What Cities could/should do at a national level to contribute with the deployment of the highly automated vehicles?

Entrez votre réponse

Annex 2: Questionnaire on Use case and Scenarios

A) General information on use cases:

- 1) What are your use cases for testing and validating a Connected and Automated Vehicle? (these use cases will be used in the following questions)
- 2) Do you think the use cases that you are currently working on are priority compared to other use cases (e.g. Highway pilot, Valet parking, urban driving, truck platooning ...)? Why?
- 3) What are the benefits associated to your use cases?
- 4) What do you think of the social acceptance for these use cases (accepted in 3 / 7 / 15 years)?
- 5) What are the risks associated to your use cases? (e.g. risks on connectivity, different infrastructures...)
- 6) What are your minimum system requirements for these use cases? (e.g. Have only one camera. Mandatory 2 technologies for 2 sensors)
- 7) What are the associated performances/limitations for the system? Ex: not working by night (ODD).
- 8) What MRM (Minimum Risk Manoeuvre) and HMI (Human-Machine Interface) do you consider for your use cases?

B) Use case specification:

- 9) What kind of infrastructure/road is needed for your use cases?

Do you see any change in infrastructure useful to help the implementation of these use cases?

- 10) What kind of traffic is needed for these use cases?

- 11) What are the laws in your country to test your use cases?

What experimentation area is needed?

C) Procedures & Methodology

12) What procedures and tools could be used to test your use cases?

13) What methodology would you like to use for certification?

14) What are the benefits and disadvantages of testing CAD on test track and open road vs. simulation for this use case / scenarios?

How do you link test instances (proving ground, simulation, real world field test)?

D) Certification/homologation

15) In your opinion, what are the priority use cases for certification and homologation?

Online survey on Use cases and Scenarios

Use Cases & Scenarios

INTRODUCTION

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1. What kind of stakeholder would you consider your organization? *

- OEM
- Automotive supplier
- Regulatory entity
- Testing facility
- Consumer organisation
- Research institute
-

2. What are your use cases for testing and validation for a Connected and Automated Vehicle (CAV)? *

- Use-cases (these use cases will be used in the following questions)
- Highway pilot (SAE lvl 3 and 4)
- Traffic jam pilot (SAE lvl 3 and 4)
- Urban driving (SAE lvl 3 and 4)
- Truck platooning
- Robot taxi (SAE lvl 4 and 5)
- Automated shuttle (SAE lvl 5)
- Valet parking
-

3. Precise the Autonomy level (SAE). *

4. Precise the Operational Design Domain (ODD): *

Highway

Urban

Parking

Autre

5. Which of these use-cases will be out on the market first? *

Entrez votre réponse

6. On what priority use case do you want to focus the interview? *

Entrez votre réponse

7. What are the benefits associated to your priority use-cases? *

Comfort

Safety

Environmental benefit

Saving costs

Reducing fuel consumption

Improving the traffic

Autre

8. What do you think of the social acceptability of the following use cases once they are out on the market? *

	immediately accepted	between 0 and 3 years	between 3 and 7 years	between 7 and 15 years	more than 15 years
Highway pilot (SAE lvl 3 and 4)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Traffic jam pilot (SAE lvl 3 and 4)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Urban driving (SAE lvl 3 and 4)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Truck platooning	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Robot taxi (SAE lvl 4 and 5)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Automated shuttle (SAE lvl 5)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Valet parking	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Other	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

9. How could the road infrastructure change to accompany the evolution of CAV? *

10. What MRM (Minimum Risk Manoeuvre) do you consider for your priority use-cases? *

11. What HMI (Human-Machine Interface) do you consider for your priority use-cases? *

12. Are your main use cases concerned by the following topics? *

- Cyber-security
- V2X communication
- Positioning

13. What methodology would you like to see for CAV certification? *

Entrez votre réponse

14. What are the benefits and disadvantages of testing CAV on test track and open road vs. simulation? *

Entrez votre réponse

15. How would you link these three test instances? *

Entrez votre réponse

16. Do you have any additional comments on the topic of Use cases and Scenarios? *

Entrez votre réponse

17. Do you want your answers to stay anonymous? *

- Yes
- No

Annex 3: Questionnaire on Safety Assessment and Safety-Case

A) Safety Risks

1) What are the new risks/hazards introduced by Connected and Automated Vehicles (for any use case at SAE level 3, 4 & 5)?

2) What are your objectives for testing CAD safety?

Qualitative objectives:

Quantitative objectives:

3) Do you think the scenario-based approach should be used to validate CAD safety? Why?

4) What are the scenarios for your use cases to assess the safety of a CAD?

B) Testing Procedures & Methodology

5) What testing procedures and tools are needed for assessing the safety of a CAD?

6) What methodology are you using for assessing the safety of a CAD? How to prove that it is enough? Using the SOTIF (ISO PAS 21448)?

7) What kind of data can be collected for the safety of CAD?

Is a Black Box needed?

8) What data from Field Operational Tests can be collected for improving the CAD safety?

C) Testing CAD safety

9) What are the current standards and regulations to take into account for the validation of CAD Safety?

10) What to change first in the legislation to guarantee the safety of CAD (connectivity with infrastructure /cyber security ...)?

Online survey on Safety assessment and safety case

Safety Assessment & Safety-Case

INTRODUCTION

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1. What are the new risks/hazards introduced by Connected and Automated Vehicles (for any use case at SAE level 3, 4 & 5)? *

2. What are your objectives for testing CAV safety? (i. qualitative and ii. quantitative) *

3. Do you think the scenario-based approach should be used to validate CAV safety? *

Yes

No

4. Please justify your answer. *

5. What testing procedures and tools can be used for CAV testing? *

Entrez votre réponse

6. What methodology are you using for testing the safety of a CAV? *

Entrez votre réponse

7. How to prove that it is enough? *

Entrez votre réponse

8. What data from Field Operational Tests can be used to further improve CAV safety? *

Entrez votre réponse

9. Do you think recording data with a black box system is needed to improve the safety of CAV? *

Yes

No

10. If you answered yes in the question above, what kind of data would be needed?

Entrez votre réponse

11. What are the current standards and regulations to take into account for testing CAV Safety? At (i) national level and (ii) an international level. *

Entrez votre réponse

12. What to change first in the legislation to guarantee the safety of CAV? *

Entrez votre réponse

13. Do you have any additional comments on the topic of Connected and Automated Vehicles (CAV) Safety? *

Entrez votre réponse

14. Do you want your answers to stay anonymous? *

Yes

No

Annex 4: Questionnaire on Testing

- 1) How do you position yourself, what category of stakeholder?
 - a. OEM / Tiers
 - b. Consumer Assessment
 - c. Member states and type approval technical services
 - d. Research Institute
- 2) What testing capabilities do you support?
 - a. Virtual Simulations
 - b. Driving Simulators
 - c. Proving Ground
 - d. Field Operational Tests
 - e. Naturalistic Driving Studies
 - f. Other?
- 3) What equipment do you use on proving grounds?
 - a. Balloon Cars
 - b. UFO Target (Driving Balloon Car Platform)
 - c. Robot for Pedestrians
 - d. Steering Robot
 - e. Pedal Robot
 - f. Virtual Components (Vehicle in the Loop)
 - g. Others?
- 4) What proving ground environment (ODD) do you have?
 - a. Urban
 - b. Rural
 - c. Highway
 - d. Parking
 - e. Intersections
 - f. Roundabouts
 - g. Others?
- 5) Further capabilities for proving grounds?
 - a. Traffic lights

- b. Traffic signs
 - c. Lane markings (dynamic?)
 - d. Slope
 - e. Others?
- 6) On what SAE level do you test?
- 7) What types of tests do you conduct?
 - a. ODD?
 - b. Type
 - i. Safety Assurance,
 - ii. Performance,
 - iii. Validation,
 - iv. HMI,
 - v. Customer Clinics,
 - vi. Sensor Tests,
 - vii. Others?
 - c. Further concretisation?
- 8) What tools/toolchain do you utilize?
- 9) Do you conduct tests regarding Cyber-Security, Positioning or Communication?
- 10) If (9) yes → How do you test these technologies?
- 11) What methodology do you use to test?
- 12) Do you use different methodologies for proving grounds and simulations?
- 13) How do you allocate scenarios between simulation, proving ground and field test?

Online survey on Testing

Testing

INTRODUCTION

HEADSTART (Harmonised European Solutions for Testing Automated Road Transport) is a new European initiative that aims to define testing and validation procedures on specific functionalities of Connected and Automated Driving (CAD). HEADSTART will define testing and validation procedures of functions including its key enabling technologies by cross-linking of all test instances such as simulation, proving ground and real-world field tests to validate safety and security performance according to the needs of key user groups (technology developers, consumer testing and type approval).

The current stage in the project is to define and develop test, validation and certification methodologies and procedures for CAD building upon existing initiatives. HEADSTART will develop testing, validation and certification methodologies and procedures for CAD by: closing existing gaps and developing methodologies, procedures and tools beyond state-of-the-art. For the gaps identified, HEADSTART will develop methodologies, procedures and tools for the testing and validation of highly automated functions and its KET's according to stakeholder requirements, current state-of-the-art and in coordination with ongoing initiatives.

PURPOSE OF QUESTIONNAIRE

In order to enable HEADSTART to "develop testing, validation and certification methodologies and procedures for CAD by: closing existing gaps and developing methodologies, procedures and tools beyond state-of-the-art." The purpose of this survey is to collect the Stakeholders needs (e.g. OEM, Automotive Suppliers, Testing facility, Regulatory Entity) on methodologies, procedures, tools and standards for demonstrations and certifications of different use-cases. Results of this survey will be used to build a prioritisation of use-cases that will be reviewed by different user groups through a workshop.

Read more about HEADSTART on <https://www.headstart-project.eu/>

Read the survey's privacy policy here: <https://www.headstart-project.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/06/online-surveys-privacy-policy.pdf>

1. How do you position yourself, what category of stakeholder? *

- OEM / Tiers
- Consumer Assessment
- Member states and type approval technical services
- Research Institute

2. What testing capabilities do you support? *

- Virtual Simulations
- Driving Simulators
- Proving Ground
- Field Operational Tests
- Naturalistic Driving Studies
-

3. What equipment do you use on proving grounds? *

- Balloon Cars
- UFO Target (Driving Balloon Car Platform)
- Robot for Pedestrians
- Steering Robot
- Pedal Robot
- Virtual Components (Vehicle in the Loop)
-

4. What proving ground environment (ODD) do you have? *

- Urban
- Rural
- Highway
- Parking
- Intersections
- Roundabouts
-

5. Further capabilities for proving grounds? *

- Traffic lights
- Traffic signs
- Lane markings
- Slope
-

6. On what SAE level do you test? *

7. What types of tests do you conduct? *

- ODD
- Safety Assurance
- Performance
- Validation
- HMI
- Customer Clinics
- Sensor Tests
- Further concretisation
- Autre

8. What tools/toolchain do you utilize? *

9. Do you conduct tests regarding Cyber-Security, Positioning or Communication? In case of a positive response, please justify how you test these technologies. *

10. What methodology do you use to test? *

11. Do you use different methodologies for proving grounds and simulations? *

12. How do you allocate scenarios between simulation, proving ground and field test? *

Annex 5: Questionnaire on Consumer testing

1) Starting from these definitions:

- **Safety benefit:** how many lives could be saved and accidents avoided by the AD function
- **Safety assurance:** the function is able to perform as expected, without adding risk to the driver or other road users

What is the purpose to perform consumer testing about Automated Driving functions (AD)?
Which differences do you expect between type approval and consumer testing for AD?

_____ open answer

2) Explain if and why the following topics should be assessed during the consumer tests for AD:

- **Driving performance of the function (capabilities like breaking or steering...)**

_____ open answer

- **Comfort**

_____ open answer

- **Safety assurance & reliability (in terms of functionalities and malfunctioning)**

_____ open answer

- **Information given to the customers (vehicle manual and marketing campaigns)**

_____ open answer

- **HMI inside the car while driving**

_____ open answer

- **Cyber security**

_____ open answer

3) SAE levels definition is a good way to cluster AD functions for automotive technician?

Yes

No

And for customers?

Yes

No

if you want to precise your answer: _____ open answer

4) Do you think the conventional and actual star rating should be used for higher levels of automation?

Yes

No

if you want to precise your answer: _____ open answer

5) Should the same scenario & criteria be applied regardless of level of automation?

- Yes
- No

if you want to precise your answer: _____ open answer

6) Euro NCAP has defined three group AD functions and four domains:

- Assisted / Automated / Autonomous
- Domain: parking / city / inter-urban / highway

Do you think it is better:

- to define separate scores and methodologies for each possible combination level-domain
- to have an overall evaluation

if you want to precise your answer: _____ open answer

7) It would be important to obtain:

- a single value score to compare different vehicles;
- Check if some requirements are satisfied or not (pass/fail mode).

if you want to precise your answer: _____ open answer

8) How should consumer testing combine scenarios to different testing methodologies such as Simulations (x In the Loop), track tests, open road tests during the evaluation?

_____ open answer

9) How should the consumer testing scenario be selected and prioritized?

_____ open answer

10) What do you think is the expected time to be assessed by consumer testing functions dealing with:

- Level 3: _____
- Level 4: _____
- V2x communication for AD functions: _____
- Driver Monitoring systems for AD functions: _____

11) What do you think is the expected time for L3+ functions to be assessed by consumer testing functions dealing with:

- Highways: _____
- Urban: _____
- Inter-urban: _____
- Parking: _____

12) Should the AD function be tested outside the ODD?

_____ open answer

13) How should the limitations of the function be communicated to the public?

_____ open answer

Online survey on Consumer testing

Consumer Testing

INTRODUCTION

HEADSTART (Harmonised European Solutions for Testing Automated Road Transport) is a new European initiative that aims to define testing and validation procedures on specific functionalities of Connected and Automated Driving (CAD). HEADSTART will define testing and validation procedures of functions including its key enabling technologies by cross-linking of all test instances such as simulation, proving ground and real-world field tests to validate safety and security performance according to the needs of key user groups (technology developers, consumer testing and type approval).

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PURPOSE OF QUESTIONNAIRE

In order to enable HEADSTART to "develop testing, validation and certification methodologies and procedures for CAD by: closing existing gaps and developing methodologies, procedures and tools beyond state-of-the-art." The purpose of this survey is to collect the Stakeholders needs (e.g. OEM, Automotive Suppliers, Testing facility, Regulatory Entity) on methodologies, procedures, tools and standards for demonstrations and certifications of different use-cases. Results of this survey will be used to build a prioritisation of use-cases that will be reviewed by different user groups through a workshop.

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1. Starting from these definitions:

- Safety benefit: how many lives could be saved and accidents avoided by the AD function
- Safety assurance: the function is able to perform as expected, without adding risk to the driver or other road users

What is the purpose to perform consumer testing about Automated Driving functions (AD)?

Which differences do you expect between type approval and consumer testing for AD? *

Entrez votre réponse

2. Driving performance of the function (capabilities like breaking or steering...) *

Entrez votre réponse

3. Comfort *

Entrez votre réponse

4. Safety assurance & reliability (in terms of functionalities and malfunctioning) *

Entrez votre réponse

5. Information given to the customers (vehicle manual and marketing campaigns) *

Entrez votre réponse

6. HMI inside the car while driving *

Entrez votre réponse

7. Cyber security *

Entrez votre réponse

8. SAE levels definition is a good way to cluster AD functions for automotive technician? *

Yes

No

Autre

9. And for customers? *

Yes

No

Autre

10. Do you think the conventional and actual star rating should be used for higher levels of automation? *

- Yes
- No
-

11. Should the same scenario & criteria be applied regardless of level of automation? *

- Yes
- No
-

12. Euro NCAP has defined three group AD functions and four domains:

- Assisted / Automated / Autonomous
- Domain: parking / city / inter-urban / highway

Do you think it is better: *

- to define separate scores and methodologies for each possible combination level-domain
- to have an overall evaluation
-

13. It would be important to obtain: *

- a single value score to compare different vehicles;
- Check if some requirements are satisfied or not (pass/fail mode).
-

14. How should consumer testing combine scenarios to different testing methodologies such as Simulations (x in the loop), track tests, open road test during the evaluation?

15. How should the consumer testing scenario be selected and prioritized? *

What do you think is the expected time to be assessed by consumer testing functions dealing with:

16. Level 3: *

17. Level 4: *

18. V2x communication for AD functions: *

19. Driver Monitoring systems for AD functions *

What do you think is the expected time for L3+ functions to be assessed by consumer testing functions dealing with:

20. Highways *

21. Urban *

22. Inter-urban *

23. Parking *

24. Should the AD function be tested outside the ODD? *

Entrez votre réponse

25. How should the limitations of the function be communicated to the public? *

Entrez votre réponse

Annex 6: Online survey: Testing goals for KETs

Use cases and existing gaps for testing communication, cyber-security and positioning

INTRODUCTION

Harmonized European Solutions for Testing Automated Road Transport (HEADSTART) <https://www.headstart-project.eu/> HEADSTART will define testing and validation procedures of functions including its key enabling technologies by cross-linking of all test instances such as simulation, proving ground and real-world field tests to validate safety and security performance according to the needs of key user groups (technology developers, consumer testing and type approval).

THE STEP OF DEFINING WHAT TO DEVELOP

The current stage in the project is to define and develop test, validation and certification methodologies and procedures for CAD building upon existing initiatives. HEADSTART will develop testing, validation and certification methodologies and procedures for CAD by: closing existing gaps and developing methodologies, procedures and tools beyond state-of-the-art. For the gaps identified, HEADSTART will develop methodologies, procedures and tools for the testing and validation of highly automated functions and its KET's according to stakeholder requirements, current state-of-the-art and in coordination with ongoing initiatives.

PURPOSE OF QUESTIONNAIRE

In order to enable HEADSTART to "develop testing, validation and certification methodologies and procedures for CAD by: closing existing gaps and developing methodologies, procedures and tools beyond state-of-the-art."

The specific purpose of this questionnaire is to collect the Stakeholders (ex : OEM, Tier 1, Testing facility, Regulatory) use case, with the specific associated testing needs with regards to communication, cyber-security, positioning. Requirements will be extracted from the elaborated testing needs and used to create a catalogue of the (new) testable aspects of KET's (i.e. communication, cyber-security, positioning), that is not competently satisfied (or that has some aspects that need developing) under the current testing methodologies (paradigm).

INSTRUCTIONS

One use case per form, if there are more than one use case please feel free to submit multiple forms. Specific contact information is of course optional and will be handled with discretion.

1. Name of responding organization and person.

Any contact information is optional and will only be used for the specific purpose stated above. When responses are aggregated, all personal information will be discarded.

Entrez votre réponse

2. Formulate a name for your high level use case/user need: *

Example: Truck platooning in an urban environment, automation level 4 in urban, if applicable one could also put down the commercial name or alternatively research project name.

Entrez votre réponse

3. Description of the user need *

Example: In an urban environment, positioning is used by CAVs to plan trajectories avoiding collisions with static obstacles and other road users (pedestrians, cyclists, vehicles). Hence, inaccurate positioning would result in additional safety margins to be included in such planning. Also the communication and cybersecurity needs to be considered.

Entrez votre réponse

4. What kind of stake-hold would you consider is of primary concern for your user need? *

- Testing and validation (development): OEMs, Tier1s as well as other development stakeholders that require cost-time effective and robust methods and tools for the testing and validation of CAD vehicles.
- Assessment: Consumer testing (e.g. Euro NCAP) that have a proven impact in the dissemination and adoption of safety features among users and industry.
- Certification (type approval): Member states and type approval technical services that require a trustworthy procedure to determine safety of the vehicles before allowing them to be introduced on roads.

5. What kind of stakeholder would you consider your organization in this context? *

- OEM
- Tier 1 supplier
- Tier 2 supplier
- Tool provider
- Regulatory entity
- Testing facility
- Research institute
-

6. Which Ertrac category does the use case mostly belong to? *

<https://www.ertrac.org/uploads/documentsearch/id57/ERTRAC-CAD-Roadmap-2019.pdf>

- Automated Freight Vehicles
- Automated Passenger Cars
- Urban Mobility Vehicles
-

7. In case you answered Automated Freight Vehicles, which automated freight vehicle applications does the use case fit best

Levels refer to the automation levels in SAE J 3016

- C-ACC Platooning (Level 1)
- Parking Garage Pilot (Level 4)
- Automated Truck Platooning (Level 2)
- Highway Pilot platooning (Level 4)
- Traffic Jam Assist (Level 2)
- Traffic Jam Chauffeur (Level 3)
- Highway Chauffeur (Level 3)
- Highly automated freight vehicles in Confined Areas (Level 4)
- Highly automated freight vehicles in Hub-to-Hub operation (Level 4)
- Highly automated freight vehicles on Open Roads and Urban (Level 4)
- Fully automated freight vehicles (Level 5)

8. In case you answered Automated Passenger Cars, in which automated passenger car application does the use case fit best?

Levels refer to the automation levels in SAE J 3016.

- Parking Assist (Level 2)
- Parking Garage Pilot (Level 4)
- Automated Valet Parking (Level 4)
- Traffic Jam Assist (Level 2)
- Traffic Jam Chauffeur (Level 3)
- Highway Chauffeur (Level 3)
- Urban and Suburban Pilot (Level 4)
- Highway Autopilot (Level 4)
- Highway Convoy (Level 4)
- Autonomous private vehicles on public roads (Level 5)

9. In case you answered urban mobility vehicles, which urban mobility vehicle applications does the use case fit best?

Levels refer to the automation levels in SAE J 3016.

- Parking Assistance (Level 2)
- Traffic Jam Assist (Level 2)
- Urban Bus Assist (Level 2)
- Automated Bus Chauffeur (Level 3)
- Automated PRT/Shuttles on dedicated roads (Level 4)
- Automated PRT/Shuttles in mixed traffic (Level 4)
- Highly Automated Buses on Dedicated Lane (Level 4)
- Highly Automated Buses in Mixed Traffic (Level 4)
- Fully Automated Urban Vehicles (Level 5)

10. If Ertrac categorise do not capture the use case please elaborate on this.

Entrez votre réponse

11. What key enabling technologies are of most interest here? *

Since all technologies probably are relevant to all use cases, a ranking would give an indication of the most pressing concern.

Cybersecurity
Positioning
Communication

12. What is most relevant test propose for the key enabling technologies? *

A variation on question 4, but here specific to key enabling technologies that could be different.

- Verification
- Validation
- Certification
- Assessment (consumer testing)
- Assessment required by standards e.g. independent cybersecurity or functional safety assessment
- Autre

13. Elaboration on the most relevant test propose (previous question) if applicable. *

- Concept evaluation and development
- Correctness of implementation and of specification
- Robustness
- Correct implementation and consistency of interfaces
- Effectiveness of safety mechanisms
- Functional performance
- Regulatory requirement fulfillment
-

14. Is there some specific KET requirement you can put a quantitative or qualitative number on? *

15. Elaborate if there is some specific testing need related to KET's, that you see as extra challenging to fulfill. *

16. If there are any specific feedback on the construction of the form please provide it here. *

Harmonised European Solutions for Testing Automation Road Transport

Disclaimer:

Content reflects only the authors' view and European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.